

ALFA
UNLOCKING THE BIOGAS POTENTIAL
OF LIVESTOCK FARMING

D2.2

Co-Creation outcomes shaped to our stakeholders needs

WR Research

31 / 08 / 2023

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EDITORS	Pol Camps, Sofia Michopoulou (WR)
AUTHORS (Organisation)	Pol Camps, Sofia Michopoulou (WR) Andromachi Kalaouzi, George Efraimidis, George Tsogas (Q-PLAN) Stania Druskova (PEDAL) Carla Sebastiani (SIE) Flaminia Rocca (APRE) Enrico Facci (A0C02) Michael Stöckler (FBCD)
REVIEWERS	Carla Sebastiani (SIE) Stanislava Druskova (PEDAL)
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Executive Summary

The present deliverable reports the outcomes of each co-creation workshop organised by the ALFA project. These events had the goal of co-creating the project's support services portfolio to enhance the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming across the target regions.

A common methodology, structure and co-creation tools were used across the co-creation workshops of each ALFA hub. The workshops included one background session and two co-creation sessions. The background session was used to (i) present the ALFA project along with its initial results and the support services portfolio, and (ii) to offer information about each region's specific situation regarding current barriers, enablers and needs to the uptake of biogas technologies in livestock farming. During the co-creation sessions, participants validated and ranked a list of barriers, needs and support measures related to the enhancement of the adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming. The top-prioritized regional areas of improvement were selected for further discussion: support plans to implement them were co-created together with the definition of the impact's evaluation framework and the identification of practical issues during the implementation.

The outcomes of each workshop are outlined in this report. The organisation of a co-creation workshop was conducted in each of the 6 project's regional hubs: Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, and Spain. These workshops engaged regional stakeholders from each of the quadruple helix categories (including industry actors, such as livestock farmers and biogas plant owners, authorities, social organisations and researchers). Based on the discussions among the participants, each Alfa hub was able to draft support plans for implementing the support services, also identifying the expected barriers and impact during the implementation, among other aspects.

In a nutshell, the comparative analysis of the required support services in ALFA's target countries reveals key focus areas that are crucial for promoting the adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming. Business support emerges as a vital aspect, with administrative assistance and financial evaluation being top priorities. Access to finance also poses a significant challenge in certain countries like Greece and Slovakia, highlighting the need for tailored solutions to overcome this obstacle. Technical support plays also a critical role in ensuring that potential biogas producers feel confident in the efficient operation and maintenance of biogas systems, with expert consultancy and digestate handling assistance being particularly essential. Overall, raising awareness is identified as a common requirement, where success stories, case studies, and targeted educational materials are sought to cultivate public acceptance and support. Additionally, capacity-building initiatives should focus on engaging stakeholders effectively through workshops, seminars, and collaborations with relevant associations. Overall, participants' valuable recommendations underscore the significance of collaboration with external partners and knowledge sharing to maximize the impact of the ALFA project.

Building upon the findings of the co-creation workshops, ALFA's upcoming activities will focus on preparing a refined and regionally-tailored portfolio of support measures, including business and technical services, awareness-raising campaigns and capacity-building activities. Such measures will be offered to livestock farmers and other actors interested in investing in biogas systems during next stages of the project. To find these potential beneficiaries, ALFA will run the first of two rounds of open calls in the following months.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....9

2. METHODOLOGY10

 2.1 Focus of the event and target groups 10

 2.2 Preparatory work 10

 2.3 Workshop’s structure..... 12

 2.4 Informative material..... 16

 2.5 Reporting templates 17

3. DELIVERING THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS17

 3.1 Co-creation Workshop in Belgium 18

 3.1.1 Workshop’s general information 18

 3.1.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented20

 3.1.3 Detailed remarks from Session 121

 3.1.4 Detailed remarks from Session 225

 3.1.5 Closing session30

 3.1.6 Communication and Dissemination30

 3.1.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities.....31

 3.2 Co-creation Workshop in Denmark..... 32

 3.2.1 Workshop’s general information32

 3.2.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented33

 3.2.3 Detailed remarks34

 3.2.4 Communication and Dissemination38

 3.2.5 Material and multimedia produced during the activities.....39

 3.3 Co-creation Workshop in Greece 40

 3.3.1 Workshop’s general information40

 3.3.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented42

 3.3.3 Detailed remarks from Session 143

 3.3.4 Detailed remarks from Session 246

 3.3.5 Closing session49

 3.3.6 Communication and Dissemination50

 3.3.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities.....50

 3.4 Co-creation Workshop in Italy 51

 3.4.1 Workshop’s general information51

3.4.2	Participants and stakeholder groups represented	52
3.4.3	Detailed remarks from Session 1	53
3.4.4	Detailed remarks from Session 2	56
3.4.5	Closing session	63
3.4.6	Communication and Dissemination	63
3.4.7	Material and multimedia produced during the activities	64
3.5	Co-creation Workshop in Slovakia	64
3.5.1	Workshop’s general information	64
3.5.2	Participants and stakeholder groups represented	66
3.5.3	Detailed remarks from Session 1	68
3.5.4	Detailed remarks from Session 2	72
3.5.5	Closing session	79
3.5.6	Communication and Dissemination	80
3.5.7	Material and multimedia produced during the activities	81
3.6	Co-creation Workshop in Spain	81
3.6.1	Workshop’s general information	81
3.6.2	Participants and stakeholder groups represented	82
3.6.3	Detailed remarks from Session 1	84
3.6.4	Detailed remarks from Session 2	87
3.6.5	Closing session	91
3.6.6	Communication and Dissemination	92
3.6.7	Material and multimedia produced during the activities	93
4.	DISCUSSION OF CO-CREATED SUPPORT PLANS	95
5.	CONCLUSIONS	106
6.	ANNEXES	107
6.1	Annex I – Workshop’s agenda	107
6.2	Annex II - Reporting template	108

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Visual summary of the co-creation workshops' objectives, methods and other characteristics	9
Figure 2. Overview of the Miro board template created for the online co-creation workshops	13
Figure 3. Example of the whiteboard focused on the top priorities created for both the onsite and online co-creation workshops.....	15
Figure 4. Example of slides for the co-creation workshops, presenting background information about the country's current situation regarding the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming	16
Figure 5. Examples of the dissemination material produced before and during the co-creation workshop in Belgium	31
Figure 6. Example of website post for the Danish workshop	39
Figure 7. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Denmark ..	40
Figure 8. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Greece	51
Figure 9. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Italian workshop	63
Figure 10. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Italy.....	63
Figure 9. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Italian workshop	63
Figure 10. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Italy	64
Figure 11. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Slovakia ..	81
Figure 12. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Spanish workshop	81
Figure 12. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Spanish workshop	92
Figure 13. The agenda of the Spanish workshop.....	93
Figure 14. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Spain	94
Figure 15. The agenda template of the workshops	107

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Main information about the co-creation workshops.....	18
Table 2. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Belgium categorized by the CHML methodology	23
Table 3. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Belgium	25
Table 4. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Belgium	26
Table 5. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Belgium.....	27
Table 6. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Belgium	29
Table 7. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Denmark categorized by the CHML methodology	36
Table 8. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Greece categorized by the CHML methodology	44
Table 9. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Greece	46
Table 10. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Greece.....	47
Table 11. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Greece	48
Table 12. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Greece	49
Table 13. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Italy categorized by the CHML methodology	55
Table 14. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Italy	57
Table 15. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Italy	58

Table 16. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Italy	60
Table 17. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Italy	62
Table 18. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Slovakia categorized by the CHML methodology	70
Table 19. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Slovakia ..	72
Table 20. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Slovakia.....	74
Table 21. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Slovakia	75
Table 22. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Slovakia	78
Table 23. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Spain categorized by the CHML methodology	86
Table 24. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Spain	88
Table 25. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Spain	89
Table 26. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Spain.....	90
Table 27. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Spain.....	91

ABBREVIATIONS

AU	Aarhus University
BPM	Biochemical Methane Potential
CCW	Co-creation workshop
CIB	Consorzio Italiano Biogas
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
EBA	European Biogas Association
EDF	European Dairy Farmers
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HABIO	Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
N, N₂	Nitrogen
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ROI	Return On Investment
VR	Virtual Reality

1. Introduction

This report provides a summary of the goals, approach, activities, and outcomes of the regional co-creation workshops organized by ALFA as part of Task 2.2 “Co-creation of solutions for biogas market uptake shaped to regional specificities and needs”. The primary aim of Task 2.2 was to arrange and facilitate co-creation workshops in each ALFA hub, with the purpose of collaboratively designing services and other measures to support the adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming.

These co-creation workshops comprised interactive and collaborative activities, fostering discussions on support strategies to encourage the implementation of biogas technologies and enhance the sustainability of the livestock sector. Furthermore, during these workshops, we shared the initial findings of the project and presented case studies identified in Task 1.3 “Study of real-life successful cases of farms uptake of biogas solutions” on both the project’s [website](#) and social media, and they will soon be included in the related deliverable that is currently undergoing review. These case studies served as inspiration for the dialogues and brainstorming sessions.

In total, 6 co-creation workshops took place, with participants representing the quadruple helix stakeholder groups, including actors from the biogas industry, authorities, civil society, and academics. Initially, the target was to have 15 participants per workshop.

Figure 1 summarises all these aspects and goals in a visual manner.

Figure 1. Visual summary of the co-creation workshops' objectives, methods and other characteristics

The responsible partners of each ALFA hub organized and facilitated the workshops, with WR Research leading as the task leader and manager of the Belgian hub. Throughout the co-creation process, WR Research provided guidance to the regional hubs by designing the methodology, preparing co-creation tools, and developing necessary guidelines. As part of the preparation phase, WR Research conducted a training session to thoroughly explain each step of the co-creation process to the project partners, offering practical guidelines for tool usage and required materials.

This deliverable consolidates the outcomes from the various workshops conducted in each region. The findings in this report will serve as a foundation for Task 2.4 “Iterative development of the ALFA market uptake support measures” activities, which involve developing and refining the essential materials and tools for delivering the project's support services. Additionally, it will support the initiatives of Task 4.2 “Mutual learning and good practices exchange”, which aims to organize mutual

learning workshops for exchanging good practices, allowing us to learn from experiences in other regions and gain a deeper understanding of the impact of our support measures.

The report's structure includes a detailed methodology in Section 2, encompassing the guidelines and materials prepared for the co-creation workshops. Section 3 provides an overview of all the co-creation workshops held in different ALFA hubs, briefly describing their characteristics and formats. Furthermore, Section 4 describes the selected measures and proposed support plans from participants in each workshop. Finally, Section 5 presents the major conclusions drawn from all the co-creation workshops.

2. Methodology

2.1 Focus of the event and target groups

Under the framework of ALFA's Task 2.2 "Co-creation of solutions for biogas market uptake shaped to regional specificities and needs", co-creation workshops were conducted to engage key stakeholders involved in the biogas value chain. The primary objective was to collaboratively develop support plans aimed at promoting the adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming. These workshops facilitated constructive discussions and feedback through collaborative brainstorming sessions.

The workshops targeted regional stakeholders representing each quadrant of the quadruple helix framework, including industry actors, academia, governmental bodies, and social organizations. Participants were chosen based on their expertise and knowledge of specific characteristics and challenges related to biogas system adoption in livestock farming, as well as familiarity with relevant governmental policies.

To ensure meaningful participation, the initial goal was to have at least 15 experts per co-creation workshop, none of whom belonged to any of the project partner organizations. The presence of the Alfa Hubs spans across various European countries, including Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, and Spain. At the time of writing this report version, five out of six co-creation workshops had already been conducted. These workshops were meticulously organized and led by the responsible partners in each country, adhering to a common methodology and employing the co-creation tools described in sections 2.2 and 2.3.

2.2 Preparatory work

Prior to the commencement of the workshops, the Task 2.2 leader (WR) took on the responsibility of guiding the regional hubs through the co-creation process. This involved preparing a unified methodology, structure, and co-creation tools to be utilized across all six workshops. Specifically, WR developed guidelines, templates, and provided training to ensure partners could make the most effective use of the co-creation tools. Additionally, WR equipped partners with the necessary resources for organizing the events, including creating templates for both online and onsite workshop versions and selecting suitable platforms for interactive virtual sessions.

To facilitate these preparations, a series of preparatory meetings were scheduled between WR and the managers of the regional hubs. The initial meeting, held on May 19, 2023, involved discussions on determining the appropriate event format. Subsequently, a comprehensive training session was conducted on June 6 to provide an in-depth overview of the co-creation sessions, tools to be used, and a thorough explanation of the entire process.

During the training session, WR introduced partners to the proposed methodology and event structure for both online and onsite versions. The second training session focused on the technical and practical aspects of the workshops, enabling partners to become familiar with the tools required

for both physical and online events. The presentation encompassed all relevant guidelines pertaining to logistics and participant support.

Furthermore, WR shared relevant resources and templates with the partners, including invitation emails, printable materials, and customizable presentation resources tailored to each hub or region. In terms of interactive session tools, WR designed templates using **Mentimeter** and **Miro** software for the online version of the workshops. Additionally, WR prepared templates for printed posters to be used in the offline version of the events.

To provide clarity, Mentimeter is an online platform used for real-time polling and surveys, while Miro board offers a virtual canvas or board where participants can collaboratively contribute their ideas during the co-creation workshops. During the training session, participants had the opportunity to explore and test the Miro board and Mentimeter templates. Alongside the training session, WR also provided partners with a comprehensive document containing the organizational guidelines. Following the training session, the regional hub managers proceeded to organize their respective co-creation events, adhering to the common templates and structure.

In addition, the guiding questions for the co-creation session were developed through an iterative process, taking into account valuable input from the project partners. Moreover, Q-Plan provided a short presentation and training on how to effectively implement the Evaluation framework, ensuring a thorough and insightful evaluation process. On the other hand, SIE delivered a comprehensive presentation on the project's Support Services.

As previously mentioned, material and guidelines were prepared for two different possible event formats: online and onsite events. For both onsite and online events an appropriate duration suggested by WR would be a maximum of 3 hours, however, each partner had the option of adjusting the agenda for the respective workshop accordingly. It was also believed that having an online option would facilitate the participation of stakeholders from different parts of the country in certain cases, due to the following reasons:

- The short timeframe of the activities (from April 2023 until August 2023);
- The fact that the events were expected to take place around summertime and that, during this period of the year, it is more challenging to have experts participate in physical meetings due to vacations.

Each of the 6 regional hubs chose the most appropriate format to run a co-creation workshop in its respective region. In terms of supportive material, the following resources were used:

List of supporting material:

- Invitation e-mail;
- E-mail banner;
- Registration and consent form;
- The brief presentation of the ALFA project;
- The presentation on the main findings on regional barriers, needs, and the successful cases;
- The ALFA Support Services presentation;
- The online tools: Mentimeter and Miro board.

2.3 Workshop's structure

The regional co-creation workshops followed a common structure, albeit with two different versions for the online and onsite formats. Both formats followed a general structure with some adaptations for specific parts; the main variations between the online or offline formats related to the tools used and the timing, with onsite sessions being lengthier. In both cases, the events offered two introductory or background sessions—one about the ALFA project and the other about the situation of the biogas sector in the specific country—, followed by two co-creation sessions. Figure 13 in Annex I shows the agendas for the workshops. Below, each main session is briefly described.

First, the event presentations kicked off with a short introduction about ALFA. Regional hub managers presented background information, initial results and cased studies identified during the first phase of the project about the given country's specific situation, based on the analysis conducted in the different tasks of WP1. The results were later used as inspiration for the discussions and the brainstorming activities. Therefore, the events were also useful to present the ALFA project and its vision.

The main topics covered in the presentation included, among others, aspects related to the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming, both on an EU and country level, including the following:

- the current status regarding the uptake and use of biogas systems;
- the country's barriers that affect its potential to invest in biogas installations;
- the country's needs to enhance the uptake of biogas systems.

Lastly, insights generated during the initial phase of the project were also included, such as:

- stakeholder perceptions about participation and involvement of women in the biogas sector and the barriers they face, and
- a number of successful cases from the target countries, including a few examples from other EU countries, that have successfully adopted biogas systems.

This background had the objective to inform the discussion and have a common understanding of the current situation upon which to build during the interactive sessions.

In particular, participants were actively engaged in two interactive, co-creative sessions. Within 'Interactive session 1', participants validated and ranked several barriers and needs related to the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming. Through the Mentimeter poll, participants were invited to vote on different polls to assess each barrier/need individually using CHML methodology, and then to rank a list of barriers/needs in terms of urgency. An overview of the preliminary outcomes was presented graphically on the Miro board, in the form of a table that the moderators had populated based on the voting. The CHML table classified the different measures according to their perceived relevance into four groups: 'critical-urgency', 'high-urgency', 'medium-urgency' and 'low-urgency'. After the participants were given the chance to reposition any recommendation, the recommended measures were ranked according to the voting, and the most urgent ones were selected for further discussion during the second co-creation session. Figure 2 shows the Miro board environment depicting the entire process of interactive sessions 1 and 2.

Figure 2. Overview of the Miro board template created for the online co-creation workshops

Next, 'Interactive session 2' focused on co-creating support plans for the selected barriers and needs. Due to logistical constraints and practical considerations, the participants were not split into groups during the workshop, ensuring a streamlined and cohesive experience for all attendees. As shown in Figure 2, this entailed the development of an implementation strategy, including the specific support services required, feedback on their implementation along with the identification of the relevant barriers, and the evaluation of the actual impact. Figure 3, illustrates the support plan template for the business/financial support services specifically, however the plans for the rest of the themes investigating slightly differ in some sections. More specifically, the discussion of the selected recommendations addressed each of the aspects listed below. Each category had its own guiding questions and a box that participants were able to fill in with their input.

- **Type of ALFA business services required / Additional business services required:** Participants were asked to concisely define the specific ALFA business/financial support services needed in their region. On that note, the Miro board provided a reminder of the list of suggested services that was also presented prior to the co-creation session. This ensured that the participants could consider and build upon the previously proposed ideas while formulating their requirements for ALFA business services. Moreover, the participants were given the chance to suggest further support services required, not included in the ALFA's initial services portfolio.
- **Implementation:** Participants were asked to provide insights on tailoring business support services to cater to the unique needs of various stakeholders, including farmers and biogas producers. They were also asked to share their preferences regarding the delivery formats of these services, such as on-site training, virtual assistance, documentation, or a combination of these. Additionally, participants were encouraged to provide ideas on making business support services more accessible and inclusive, with a specific focus on achieving gender balance.
- **Impact evaluation – Indicators:** Here participants were asked to identify the metrics or indicators that would be most suitable for evaluating the effectiveness and impact of the business support services provided by the ALFA project. Furthermore, participants were encouraged to envision themselves as beneficiaries and articulate what factors would make them perceive the services' impact as positive. In the Miro board templates provided, we had already included some examples of indicators to guide the discussions, amongst which the following:
 - Number of services received/Number of seminars webinars/Number of posts**
 - Perceived risk reduction of investment in biogas**
 - Projected output of biogas systems**
 - Overall satisfaction.**
- **Impact evaluation – Questions:** Participants were also requested to consider the questions that should be posed to beneficiaries at the conclusion of the service delivery to better understand if their needs were met and to identify areas for improvement. In addition, participants were asked to provide input on the questions that should be directed to the Hubs to assess the efficiency of the service delivery process. In the Miro board templates provided, we had already included some examples of questions to guide the discussions, amongst which the following:
 - Business/Technical Services: Did the services meet your expectations? How could the application process be improved?**

- Awareness-raising campaigns: Did the seminar meet your needs? Were the topics relevant to you? Is the knowledge gained applicable to your business?
- Capacity-building programmes: Do you agree with the following statements? → I am familiar with biogas / I would be willing to support the uptake of biogas in my region.
- **Messages to focus on (Awareness raising activities support plan):** During the discussions, participants actively contributed to shaping the messages that should be emphasized in the campaigns. They deliberated on the content and purpose of these messages, considering what information should be conveyed, why it is important, when it should be communicated, to whom it should be targeted, and the most effective means of delivery.
- **Target groups (Awareness raising activities & Capacity building support plans):** Participants actively discussed and shared their insights regarding the target groups that should be prioritized in their country. The discussion revolved around identifying key stakeholders such as farmers, biogas producers, specific public entities, the general public, associations, and other relevant groups.
- **Resources (Capacity building support plan):** Participants were encouraged to share any resources they were aware of or could provide to support the ALFA project's capacity-building activities. These resources could include networks, experts, materials, or any other relevant assets that could contribute to the project's objectives.

The format of the session remained consistent in both online and onsite scenarios, with the main difference being the tools and timing employed. For online events, we utilized platforms such as Miro and Mentimeter to facilitate interactive discussions, while onsite sessions involved the use of physical posters and templates that allowed participants to contribute their ideas through handwritten responses.

Business support:

Type of ALFA business services required

Additional business services required

Implementation

Impact evaluation - Indicators

Impact evaluation - Questions

Figure 3. Example of the whiteboard focused on the top priorities created for both the onsite and online co-creation workshops

2.4 Informative material

This section provides a recap of the background material that was shared with the participants of the co-creation workshops to provide them with the necessary information for informed discussions during their co-creation activities. In addition, the regional hub managers distributed a registration form to participants, which also included a consent form.

During the workshops, the hub managers delivered a presentation that covered important contextual information related to the specific country's conditions in terms of adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming, as discussed in section 2.3. They also provided an overview of the ALFA project and presented preliminary results. These presentation slides aimed to establish a shared understanding of the current situation, laying the foundation for meaningful discussions during the co-creation sessions. Excerpts from two introductory slides used in the co-creation workshop in Belgium can be found in Figure 4, demonstrating the content provided to participants.

Figure 4. Example of slides for the co-creation workshops, presenting background information about the country's current situation regarding the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming

To ensure compliance with data protection regulations and maintain transparency, the organizers of the co-creation workshops collected contact details (full name, email, phone number) and professional information (organization, job position, field of expertise) from the participants. Consent was obtained from the participants through the use of common Google forms, where they were provided with the opportunity to give consent for the gathering and processing of their personal data. It is important to note that personal data is only included in the reported outcomes of this deliverable if explicit consent was provided. In cases where consent was not given, all results have been anonymized in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines.

2.5 Reporting templates

In order to ensure consistent reporting of the outcomes from the co-creation workshops, WR took the initiative to develop a template, which was then shared with the regional hub managers. Following the completion of their respective workshops, each partner was responsible for gathering and selecting the input received during the co-creation sessions. They then used the provided template to document the findings and submit it back to the task leader for integration into this report.

The template, detailed in Annex II, provided a structured framework for reporting on four key aspects, facilitating a comprehensive and standardized approach to capturing and presenting the workshop outcomes.

1. **General information** about the workshop, including its location, format, agenda, information on the attendees and the stakeholder categories represented, etc.;
2. The **detailed remarks** of the two interactive sessions, including a list and classification of the recommendations and a description of the support plans;
3. **Dissemination and communications** activities carried out before, during and after the event;
4. **Media content** generated during the event, including pictures (subject to participants' consent when relevant) and images of the posters or online boards filled in during the co-creation sessions, was incorporated into the respective sections.

Section 3 of this report follows the structure outlined in the reporting template and presents the outcomes of the co-creation activities from each of the workshops. It provides a detailed account of the collaborative efforts and the resulting insights and proposals generated during the workshops. Additionally, section 4 offers a concise summary and analysis of the support plans at the overall level, providing an overview of the strategic approach and highlighting key findings and recommendations.

3. Delivering the co-creation workshops

The co-creation workshops took place between June and August and involved on average 18 participants external to the project and the consortium. Following the structure of the reporting template (see section 2.5 and Annex II), this section describes the outcomes of the co-creation workshops in each of the regional hubs, reporting in detail on all the outputs from the co-creation sessions.

Table 1. Main information about the co-creation workshops

Regional hub	Organising partner	Supporting partner	Date of the event	Format chosen	Number of Participants
Belgium	WR	-	28.06.2023	Online	16
Denmark	FBCD	Aarhus University	15.08.2023	On-site	22
Greece	Q-PLAN	CERTH	28.06.2023	Online	16
Italy	APRE	A0CO2	11.07.2023	Online	15
Slovakia	PEDAL	-	20.06.2023	On-site	21
Spain	SIE	-	06.07.2023	Online	22
Total:					112

Throughout the different hubs, one of the main challenges we encountered was the difficulty of organizing an on-site event. This challenge primarily arose from the fact that most of the farmers do not reside in urban areas and have a tight schedule, making it logistically challenging to gather everyone in a single physical location. As a result, the majority of the hubs made the decision to organize an online event as a more practical and accessible alternative. This allowed us to overcome geographical barriers and ensure wider participation from farmers and stakeholders regardless of their location. The adaptation of the methodology to an online format enabled us to maintain the essence and objectives of the event while accommodating the diverse circumstances and needs of the participants.

3.1 Co-creation Workshop in Belgium

3.1.1 Workshop's general information

The Belgian co-creation Workshop took place on June 28, 2023, as an online event. The workshop was organized by White Research, whereas the methodology used for the interactive sessions of the workshop was an adapted version of the World Café format without splitting the participants in parallel groups. In addition to the common agenda and slides provided by White Research, the workshop featured a presentation from Inagro, a Belgian research and consulting company. Inagro shared insights on the EU-funded project FER-PLAY, which aims to foster the use of alternative fertilisers in agriculture and improve soils' health. During their presentation, Inagro provided a comprehensive overview of the project, including its objectives and impact. It should be noted that Inagro also assisted in reaching out to potential participants prior to the implementation of the workshop.

The event took place online via the MS Teams platform. As was done before the summer for the first intended date, a process of contacting potential interested experts was reiterated by late May. Over fifty relevant experts in the field were individually contacted, whereas the workshop was also promoted through the project's social media channels, resulting in a total of 22 registrations via the disseminated online registration form prepared by White Research.

To incentivise attendance, the agenda was reduced to 2 hours, starting at 14.30 CET, allocating most of the time to the interactive sessions. More specifically, our agenda followed the points below:

- **Introduction:** ALFA in a nutshell and Meet & Greet. First, participants introduced themselves and their work, and expressed their individual wishes for the future of the biogas sector in Belgium. Then, we briefly presented the concept and results of the project.
- **WP1 Results Presentation:** We presented the initial research results of the project on the framework conditions of the Belgian biogas in livestock farming landscape.
- **FER-PLAY: Circular fertilisers for healthy soils – Presentation by Inagro:** Inagro shared insights on the EU-funded project FER-PLAY, which aims to foster the use of alternative fertilisers in agriculture and improve soils' health
- **Presentation of ALFA support services**
- **Co-creation session 1:** Validation and ranking of the identified barriers and needs for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming based on WP1 results.
- **Coffee break**
- **Co-creation session 2:** Co-creation of support plans for each type of ALFA support measure.
- **Discussion and conclusions**

The workshop had a diverse group of 16 participants representing various backgrounds and expertise within the Belgian livestock farming and biogas industry, with participants from both the Wallonia and the Flanders regions, even from the German-speaking community. Moreover, all four quadruple helix types were well-represented. During the co-creation session, attendees actively validated and prioritized the key barriers, enablers, and needs within the biogas sector. They identified areas for improvement and collaborated to develop support services aimed at promoting the adoption of biogas systems.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

To ensure a successful workshop, we took several preparatory actions. First, we capitalized on the contacts we had gathered within the context of WP1. We made effective use of these contacts to promote the upcoming event. Additionally, recognizing the importance of expanding our reach, we actively sought to broaden our network of experts by reaching out to new contacts and stakeholders who could potentially contribute to the workshop's success. Furthermore, we designed and sent out dedicated invitation emails with visual banners to these contacts, specifically targeting them to encourage their participation in the workshop.

In addition to leveraging our WP1 contacts, we also utilized the project's social media channels and website to further promote the event. Recognizing the potential of these platforms to reach a wider audience, we shared engaging content and provided regular updates about the workshop to reach a broader audience and attract more participants. Furthermore, EDF, EBA, and the Advisory Board members from Belgium, Valbiom, and Boerenbond, actively contributed to spreading the word about the workshop, enhancing its visibility and engagement.

Furthermore, to ensure that all participants were well-informed and prepared for the workshop, we provided them with the agenda a few days prior to the event. This allowed attendees to review the topics and schedule, ensuring they were equipped with the necessary knowledge and materials to actively engage in the workshop discussions.

Moreover, in an effort to enhance the workshop's content and expertise, we proactively reached out to Inagro that agreed to co-host the event and participate by delivering a presentation on the European-funded FER-PLAY project. Their involvement brought valuable expertise and perspectives to the workshop, enriching the overall experience for all participants.

Considering the logistical challenges of coordinating participants from different regions of Belgium and their varying schedules, we made the decision to host the event online. This allowed us to overcome geographical constraints and ensure the maximum participation of interested individuals, providing a convenient and accessible platform for all attendees.

Following the conclusion of the workshop, WR compiled the main results of the workshop into an online form. To ensure comprehensive input and insights, the online form was shared with both the attendees and the registered participants who were unable to attend the workshop. This gave them the opportunity to provide their feedback and further ideas related to the workshop's content and discussions.

3.1.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented

3.1.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note-taker etc.)
Pol Camps - WR	Facilitator – Note-taker
Sofia Michopoulou - WR	Tech support – Note-taker

3.1.2.2 Participants

Participants list ¹		
Organisation	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
Biogas-E	Industry	Biogas/energy advisor
Agra-Ost	Academia/Research	Researcher
Valbiom	Civil society	Association
Heirbaut aLgriciculture	Industry	Livestock farmer
Inagro vzw	Academia/Research	Researcher

¹ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

UCLouvain	Academia/Research	Researcher
Lamote Landbouwwerken	Industry	Livestock farmer
Penders J. BV	Industry	Biogas industry (plant tech provider, biogas producer, etc.)
Inagro vzw	Academia/Research	Researcher
Independent consultant	Industry	Biogas/energy advisor
Boerenbond	Industry	Biogas/energy advisor
CETENMA	Academia/Research	Researcher
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Government	Local administration/policy-maker
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Academia/Research	Researcher
VCM	Industry/Government	Biogas/energy advisor
CETENMA	Academia/Research	Researcher

3.1.3 Detailed remarks from Session 1

3.1.3.1 List of recommendations presented to the participants

Barriers	Needs
<p>Technical Barriers: Lack of technical knowledge, Technical constraints for collecting manure, Performance of biogas plants</p>	<p>Technical Support Needs: Technical support and consulting, Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions, Concept design and development for biogas systems</p>
<p>Business/administrative Barriers: High investment costs, Lack of financial support, Investment risk, Uncertain policy framework, Complex administrative and legal procedures</p>	<p>Business/Admin Support Needs: Financial evaluation, Access to finance support, Business modelling and planning, Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions, Administrative support</p>

Social barriers: Lack of information by citizens, Low social acceptance, Lack of awareness by farmers	Awareness-raising and capacity-building activities: Awareness-raising campaigns, Capacity-building programmes
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3.1.3.2 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

During the workshop, the participants engaged in a session dedicated to identifying the main barriers and needs in biogas plant development. The prioritization of barriers resulted in different levels of urgency. Barriers identified as critically urgent included an **uncertain policy framework, complex administrative and legal procedures**, particularly in Flanders regarding permits for building biogas plants, and the **lack of financial support** in Wallonia, specifically related to Green certificates. Barriers classified as highly urgent encompassed **investment risk** and **high investment costs**.

Medium urgency barriers included **social acceptance and citizen opposition**, often arising from concerns about odours and pollution. Participants also highlighted the **lack of technical knowledge** among farmers, **technical constraints in collecting manure**, and historical **performance issues** with small and micro biogas plants. Although the latter issue has improved over the years, negative perceptions still persist among some farmers due to word-of-mouth communication among farmers about their experiences from the past. Lastly, barriers of lower urgency included a **lack of awareness among farmers** and **insufficient information available to citizens**.

Additionally, the participants highlighted further barriers specific to the German-speaking region of Belgium, which is a rural area with a low population density. These included **challenges related to connecting to distribution networks, varying retribution and remuneration for different types of renewable energy sources, increased grid fees during consumption peaks** (which happen when the engine of a small plant is started), and **the absence of a specialized laboratory for certifying new types of fertilisers** in the Walloon market.

Moreover, the **challenges surrounding the utilization of organic fertilisers and digestate** have created a complex situation for both farmers and biogas plant owners. As discussed during the session, farmers are reluctant to import organic fertilisers due to the risk of losing payments from agro-environmental schemes. Such a financial disincentive discourages farmers from incorporating more digestate into their farms, even though it is a valuable byproduct of the biogas production process.

Particularly, in terms of fertilisers, one of the attendees mentioned that the **strict regulation of organic fertilisers** under the Nitrates Directive makes it more challenging for biogas plants to utilize such fertilisers effectively. Additionally, farmers are hesitant to provide their unfermented organic residues to external biogas plants due to the limitation prohibiting them from taking back the digestate. This restriction results in the loss of valuable nutrients for the farmers, as they are compelled to use synthetic fertilisers as a more practical –albeit less sustainable– alternative.

Finally, in terms of barriers the participants also recognized the significance of addressing the **transport and distribution of biomass**, a challenge which can vary depending on the size of the farms involved. For instance, one of the attendees reported that a major barrier for large biogas plants in East Belgium is the resistance from local communities due to concerns related to transport. The transportation of residual organic products from faraway locations by heavy trucks back to the fields as digestate raises issues in rural areas with narrow roads not designed for such heavy traffic. This transportation is viewed critically by local residents, making it difficult for large biogas projects to gain acceptance and secure building permits. In contrast, smaller biogas plants that solely utilize

the farm's own residues have a smoother approval process, as they eliminate the need for additional transport. Table 2 presents the results of the classification for both the barriers and the needs.

Table 2. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Belgium categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertain policy framework Complex administrative and legal procedures Lack of financial support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment risk High investment costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social acceptance/Citizen opposition Lack of technical knowledge Performance of biogas plants Technical constraints for collecting manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of awareness by farmers Lack of information by citizens
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for the administrative path Technical support and consulting Financial evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions Access to finance support Business modelling and planning Raising technical awareness about biogas plants (Participants' recommendation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions Capacity-building programmes Awareness-raising campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept design and development for biogas systems

As illustrated in Table 2, the identified needs were categorized based on their level of urgency using the CHML methodology, as well. Under the category of critical urgency, participants emphasized the **need for support in navigating the complex administrative processes** involved in establishing biogas plants. They also highlighted the importance of **technical support and consulting to ensure proper implementation and operation**. **Accurate financial evaluations and return on investment calculations** were identified as critical factors in decision-making. Additionally, participants expressed a desire for **administrative support and clarification on specific requirements related to biogas plant implementation**.

In terms of *high urgency*, participants emphasized the **need for consultancy services to assist with the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions**. **Access to financial support** was identified as a crucial requirement, especially in regions where additional assistance is needed. Participants also stressed the importance of **technical knowledge** specific to operating biogas plants, taking into account variations based on farm size and economic capacity. **Business modelling and planning** were highlighted as significant needs, particularly for Flemish farmers who

sought clear business plans despite having relatively better access to finance. Participants also recognized the value of **farmer-to-farmer advice** as a means of knowledge sharing and learning.

Under *medium urgency*, participants emphasized the **need for comprehensive assessments** to evaluate the potential of biogas solutions on individual farms. They also highlighted the importance of **awareness-raising campaigns** to generate interest and educate farmers about the benefits and operation of biogas plants. **Capacity-building programs** were identified as valuable initiatives, with specific focus areas and target groups, such as technical knowledge for farmers and success case studies of biogas plants using manure. While of *lower urgency*, participants acknowledged the importance of **well-designed concepts for biogas systems**.

Overall, the workshop discussions emphasized the criticality of solid business plans, technical support, financial evaluation, and administrative assistance. The participants recognized the importance of knowledge sharing, capacity building, and awareness raising in facilitating successful biogas plant implementation.

3.1.3.3 Interactive Session 1 – Additional priorities provided by participants

During the workshop, participants identified certain important factors that need to be addressed for successful biogas plant implementation. One such factor is **the performance of small biogas plants**, which have been affected by a negative reputation. It was noted that in the past, some small biogas plants did not perform well, leading to a perception that persists among farmers even though it no longer reflects the current reality. Addressing this issue is crucial to dispel misconceptions and build confidence in the performance of small biogas plants.

Another major aspect highlighted by participants is the operation of biogas plants. They emphasized the **need for raising awareness among farmers** to generate interest and promote understanding of biogas as a viable option. This awareness-raising effort would serve as a first step in fostering engagement and encouraging farmers to learn more about biogas. The technical knowledge required for operating biogas plants was acknowledged as varying based on the size and economic capacity of the farm. Tailoring support and resources to address these specific needs would contribute to successful plant operation across different contexts.

3.1.3.4 Interactive Session 1 – Final ranking: Top recommendations

- **Business support:**
 1. Access to finance (Wallonia);
 2. Administrative support (Flanders);
 3. Financial evaluation and business planning.
- **Technical support:** Technical support and consulting - Technical knowledge (operation, maintenance)
- **Awareness-raising activities** about the economic, social and environmental benefits of biogas
- **Capacity-building programmes** on plant operation and maintenance for farmers.

3.1.4 Detailed remarks from Session 2

3.1.4.1 Business/Financial Services - Support Plan

During the workshop, participants identified several areas of improvement related to business and financial support measures in the context of biogas plants. The key areas highlighted were **financial evaluation and business planning**, **access to finance** in Wallonia, and **administrative support for obtaining building permits** in Flanders.

Regarding financial evaluation and business planning, participants stressed the importance of developing comprehensive business plans for both small and large biogas plants. These plans would serve as essential tools for guiding and ensuring the success of biogas projects.

In Flanders, a participant emphasized the need for financial support to enhance existing operational biogas plants. This support would enable these plants to serve as examples for other farmers, providing guidance on the necessary steps and procedures to initiate their own biogas projects. The participant also suggested exploring the potential of implementing more centralized biogas plant models as an alternative to the decentralized approach.

In terms of access to finance in Wallonia, participants discussed the challenges in securing regional funding for biogas plant owners. It was noted that EU financial support is primarily focused on capital expenditure (CAPEX), whereas biogas plants require support at the energy production level. The lack of green certificates, particularly for green energy produced from biogas, which is essential for financial incentives, was identified as a political issue with slow governmental response. As new elections approached, the availability of additional certificates in the near future remained uncertain. Participants considered lobbying policymakers as a potential avenue to address this issue, although it was acknowledged that this might fall beyond the scope of the ALFA project's services.

Table 3. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Belgium

<i>Business/Financial Support Services Support Plan - BE</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance (Wallonia) • Administrative support (Flanders) • Financial evaluation and business planning • Development of comprehensive business plans for biogas plants, catering to both small and large-scale projects.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide guidance and assistance in creating business plans tailored to biogas plant projects • Explore opportunities for centralized biogas plant models as an alternative to decentralized approaches • Advocate for financial support mechanisms that focus on energy production rather than capital expenditure • Engage in lobbying activities to raise awareness and address policy issues related to green certificates and financial incentives.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business opportunities

3.1.4.2 Technical Services - Support Plan

During the workshop, participants identified several aspects related to technical support services that require improvement in the implementation of biogas plants. The main areas of focus were **technical support and consulting to farmers**, as well as the **need to increase technical knowledge among farmers** regarding the operation and maintenance of biogas plants.

One key concern raised by participants was the "chicken-egg" issue in Wallonia. The lack of financial incentives for biogas investments resulted in a limited number of plants being built and thus a small market for technology providers, which, in turn, reduced the interest of potential stakeholders such as schools and universities to provide training on the subject. This perpetuates the lack of interest from policymakers to provide financial incentives, creating a cycle that hinders the growth of the biogas industry. The absence of a market for certificates or labels was also mentioned as a hindrance to biogas plant development. Participants noted that although Valbiom, the main association in Wallonia for biomass valorisation and biogas promotion, already receives government funding to address technical issues related to biogas plants, there is still a lack of interest in providing support.

Table 4. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Belgium

<i>Technical Support Services Support Plan - BE</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support and consulting for farmers in biogas plant operation and maintenance • Development of factsheets in regional languages to provide accessible information about biogas plant technologies and benefits • Research and communication on pollution issues related to biogas plants, particularly surplus ammonia emissions • Analysis of fermenter biology and gas quality to optimize biogas production.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address the "chicken-egg" issue by advocating for financial incentives and creating a market for certificates or labels • Encourage knowledge sharing and visibility through visits to successful biogas plant installations (demo units) • Provide ongoing monitoring and support to ensure optimal operation of biogas plants.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in visits to successful biogas plant installations.

To facilitate the dissemination of information, participants highlighted the **need for the development of factsheets in regional languages**. These factsheets should use clear and simple language to make information about biogas plant technologies and their benefits more accessible.

Participants also suggested offering **visits to successful biogas plant installations**, referred to as demo units. These visits would provide visibility and promote knowledge sharing among farmers. However, there were concerns about the visitor profiles, with some plant owners potentially being more reluctant to host certain stakeholders like policymakers. It was also noted that Valbiom already organizes periodic visits to biogas plants in Wallonia, accompanied by expert presentations, through its "Tour de la Biométhanisation" initiative.

Another topic of discussion was the **need for research or scientific communication regarding pollution related to biogas plants**. Specifically, participants suggested including research on surplus ammonia emissions resulting from biogas plant installations in livestock farms. Addressing this concern would involve disseminating available scientific results and evidence to provide clarity on the issue.

Additionally, participants emphasized the importance of **analysing fermenter biology and gas quality**. They recognized that feeding errors often occur in the initial months of operation, underscoring the need for careful monitoring throughout the plant's lifespan to ensure profitable operation. Strategies were also highlighted to integrate biogas production with the farm's grazing strategy during the summer months when fresh manure cannot be used as a substrate, suggesting the use of alternative sources such as grass cuttings from green areas.

3.1.4.3 Awareness raising activities - Support Plan

During the workshop, participants engaged in discussions on the implementation of awareness-raising activities to promote the benefits of biogas plants and energy. The main area of improvement identified was social acceptance and citizen opposition, closely linked to the availability of information.

Participants recognized the close relationship between low social acceptance and the lack of information regarding biogas plants. They emphasized that raising awareness and providing accurate information about biogas plants are crucial for improving social acceptance. It was noted that **the level of social acceptance varies depending on the size and type of the biogas plant**, with distinctions made between small-scale farm-based plants and large-scale centralized plants, as public perceptions differ significantly.

Table 5. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Belgium

<i>Awareness-raising Activities Support Plan - BE</i>	
Type of awareness-raising activities required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online resources and forms providing accessible information about biogas plants and their benefits • Informative videos showcasing functioning biogas plants • Organization of on-site visits to operational biogas plants.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasize accurate and reliable information to address low social acceptance and opposition • Garner support from agricultural federations and policy-makers by demonstrating the benefits of biogas plants • Leverage existing networks of research centres and agricultural partners for knowledge dissemination.
Messages to focus on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The environmental benefits of biogas plants, such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions and waste management

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The economic advantages for farmers, including additional revenue streams and cost savings • The role of biogas plants in promoting sustainable agriculture and circular economy practices • Address misconceptions and provide accurate information about biogas plant operations and benefits • Address misconceptions of regulators regarding the use of organic fertilisers
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Farmers • Researchers (for collaboration) • Municipalities • Governments (for the legislation)
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of online resource accesses and video views • Participation and feedback from on-site visits to biogas plants.

Additionally, participants stressed the importance of **convincing agricultural federations and policy-makers about the benefits of biogas plants**. Demonstrating the advantages and potential of biogas plants to these stakeholders would help garner their support and facilitate the development of favourable policies and regulations. Participants acknowledged that agricultural federations and policy-makers may hold misperceptions about biogas and its uses as fuel, and involving them in promoting biogas could ultimately benefit farmers.

To enhance awareness, participants suggested the **creation of online forms that provide accessible information about biogas plants and their benefits**. Additionally, they emphasized the effectiveness of **videos showcasing functioning biogas plants**. These videos can visually demonstrate the operations, advantages, and positive outcomes of biogas plants, making the information more engaging and relatable to the audience.

Furthermore, participants highlighted the significance of organizing **on-site visits to operational biogas plants**. These visits would allow interested individuals, including the general public, farmers, and researchers, to witness biogas plants in operation firsthand. Participants recognized that on-site visits could help dispel misconceptions, provide valuable insights, and deepen understanding of the benefits and potential of biogas plants. Specifically, on-site visits would address misconceptions held by the population, such as concerns about smell pollution, and misconceptions held by farmers, such as doubts about the functionality and effectiveness of biogas plants. It was noted that farmers are usually willing to showcase their plants, particularly to other farmers, as it fosters trust and offers an opportunity to learn from peers, which is linked to the capacity building aspect of gaining technical knowledge. However, they might be more hesitant to host visits for stakeholders like policy-makers.

In terms of target groups for awareness-raising activities, attendees mentioned the general public, municipalities, farmers, governments and researchers (as potential partners). They emphasized the **need to leverage existing networks of research centres and agricultural partners** to facilitate knowledge dissemination and reach a broader audience.

Furthermore, participants discussed the **need for administrative facilitation** to promote the use of organic fertilisers. Decisions regarding the use of organic fertilisers rest with the authorities, who often cite the negative attitude of the EU Commission towards organic fertilisers as a justification for

their actions. Additionally, participants highlighted the lack of implementation of new EU legislation and the absence of a designated reference laboratory for certifying RENURE fertilisers by local authorities.

Lastly, participants expressed interest in understanding the possibility of separating nutrients from digestate to create fertilisers specifically designed for precision farming, a topic that garnered attention and engagement during the workshop.

3.1.4.4 Capacity-building programmes - Support Plan

Capacity building emerged as a significant topic during the workshop, with participants discussing the need to enhance farmers' knowledge and skills in relation to biogas plant operation and maintenance.

First, participants recognized that **building technical knowledge among farmers is crucial** for successful biogas plant implementation. In small farms, agriculture is the primary activity, and operating a biogas plant is seen as a secondary task to generate additional income. The extra workload involved in plant operation and maintenance can be a disincentive for farmers. Additionally, hiring someone specifically for this purpose may not be economically feasible for small farms. In Flanders, where most farms have individual micro installations, farmers typically spend around 15-20 minutes per day on regular plant maintenance and rely on professional services provided by the plant technology/systems company for technical issues.

However, in Wallonia, attendees identified a challenge known as the "chicken-egg problem", where larger farms with multiple employees are more common, the low interest in biogas translates into a smaller market and a lack of service providers. This makes it challenging for farmers to find professionals to handle plant maintenance. Thus, building internal technical skills within farm teams becomes essential. However, finding professionals with the required expertise in the region is also difficult due to the lack of available courses on biogas. Therefore, offering (online) seminars on biogas plant operation and maintenance as part of capacity-building activities would address the need for technical knowledge. Partnering with regional schools that focus on hands-on skills-building courses could be a viable approach, potentially promoting existing courses or generating interest for future course offerings.

Table 6. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Belgium

<i>Capacity-building Programmes Support Plan - BE</i>	
Type of capacity-building programmes required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online seminars on biogas plant operation and maintenance for farmers • Hands-on skills-building courses in partnership with regional schools.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address the "chicken-egg problem" by emphasizing the economic benefits of biogas plant operation and maintenance for farmers • Promote existing courses or generate interest for future course offerings through partnerships with regional schools • Consider online seminars as a convenient and accessible format for capacity building.

Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts and professionals with technical expertise in biogas plant operation and maintenance • Online platforms or tools to facilitate remote learning and knowledge sharing • Collaboration with regional schools to leverage their expertise and facilities.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers, especially those operating small farms • Experts involved in biogas plant operation and maintenance • Regional schools specializing in hands-on skills training and education • Professionals interested in expanding their knowledge and skills in biogas plant maintenance and operation.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants who successfully implement the knowledge and skills acquired in their own biogas plants

Another participant emphasized the importance of **assessing whether biogas production aligns with farmers' future plans and long-term vision**. It is crucial to consider potential changes in the agricultural landscape or farm management, including the farm team, which could impact the profitability and proper functioning of the biogas plant. By evaluating these factors, farmers can make informed decisions about integrating biogas production into their long-term strategies, ensuring its viability and sustainability.

3.1.5 *Closing session*

During the closing session of the workshop, participants shared their final remarks on the conclusions drawn from the two main sessions. They expressed their appreciation for the in-depth discussions and insights gained throughout the workshop. Participants highlighted the importance of the identified barriers, needs, and potential solutions in promoting the successful implementation of biogas plants in livestock farming.

Regarding overall suggestions for the workshop, participants emphasized the need for continued knowledge exchange and capacity-building initiatives. They highlighted the significance of providing accessible information, organizing practical training sessions, and fostering networking opportunities among stakeholders in the biogas sector. Participants also stressed the importance of involving policymakers and agricultural federations to create a conducive environment for biogas plant development.

Participants were informed about future activities planned by ALFA. These activities included the provision of technical support services and the identification of suitable candidates to deliver these services. The participants showed enthusiasm and willingness to participate in ALFA's future activities, including supporting the identification and recruitment of candidates who could contribute their expertise and experience to assist in the delivery of services.

3.1.6 *Communication and Dissemination*

To ensure widespread awareness and participation, we implemented several actions to promote the workshop:

- ✓ **Dissemination via targeted e-mails:** One of the activities involved creating an email banner that was sent out to a targeted audience of a temporary, internal database which was built in the context of the ALFA initial desk research. The banner featured eye-catching visuals and concise information about the workshop, encouraging recipients to participate and learn more about the implementation of biogas plants.
- ✓ **Dissemination on project's social media:** We actively shared information and updates about the workshop on the project's social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn). This allowed us to reach a larger audience and generate interest among individuals following the project's online presence. These posts included engaging content, such as event highlights, key topics to be discussed, and registration details.
- ✓ **Dissemination via the project's website:** We utilized the website's events calendar feature, updating it with all the relevant information about our workshops. This enabled visitors to easily access details such as workshop dates, topics, and registration information.
- ✓ **Dissemination via project partners' networks:** We collaborated with the project partners European Dairy Farmers (EDF) and European Biogas Association (EBA) to effectively spread the word about the workshop among their extensive networks of members and contacts. In addition to their support, Inagro featured the event in their widely distributed newsletter, further enhancing the visibility and reach of the workshop.

For those experts who had expressed interest, communication was kept at the individual level to provide reminders, and confirm their assistance/participation.

3.1.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Figure 5. Examples of the dissemination material produced before and during the co-creation workshop in Belgium

3.2 Co-creation Workshop in Denmark

3.2.1 Workshop's general information

The Danish co-creation workshop took place as an on-site event at Aarhus University's (AU's) facilities in Foulum on Tuesday, 15th of August 2023, from 9:30 a.m. to 2 p.m. The workshop was jointly organized by Food and Bio Cluster Denmark (FBCD) and AU. The event was divided into a session in the morning with two presentations from Advisory Board members Henrik B. Møller from Aarhus University and Bruno Sander Nielsen from the Biogas Association of Denmark. After these presentations, the workshop part was conducted according to the guidelines given by White Research. The entire session was conducted with all participants gathered in the same room. Employees from FBCD moderated the whole morning's program and made sure to collect and systematize the contributions received according to the desired formats. The entire workshop part was recorded and subsequently transcribed as a supplement to the collected contributions.

After lunch, the participants went to AU's biogas plant. The facility is the world's largest experimental facility for the development and optimization of biogas processes. Advisory Board Member Henrik B. Møller is responsible for all experiments carried out at the facility. He showed around the plant and discussed about the many different activities and projects ongoing at the plant, including pre-treatment of biomass, upgrading of the biogas, methanisation, Power2x productions of methane, methanol and ammonia, ensiling and much more. The enthusiasm of the participants was very high.

The agenda for the day was:

- Reception and coffee at AU
- Welcome and purpose of the workshop
- Presentation of the participating parties
- Presentation of the latest research measures within biogas production in Denmark
- What is happening in the political area for the biogas sector?
- Presentation of the ALFA project, framework conditions, stakeholders and preliminary results, cases and support services
- Discussion about priorities, barriers, opportunities, improvements, wishes for services
- Summary and Conclusion
- Lunch and transport to the biogas plant
- Tour of the biogas plant and information on ongoing research tasks

The structure of the workshop diverged from the initially planned format of two distinct co-creation sessions. This is attributed to the nature of the event being physical, encompassing site visits, and fostering an environment where discussions naturally flowed as a unified process. The dynamic of the physical event, coupled with the interconnectedness of discussions, justified the adaptation, resulting in an effective and fluid exchange of ideas and solutions.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

The Danish Hub manager FBCD organized the workshop in collaboration with AU, which provided premises and facilities. The workshop was planned as a physical on-site event, but was changed to hybrid format that the post from Advisory Board Member Bruno Sander Nielsen could be shown online, as he was prevented from participating physically for health reasons.

The workshop was presented on FBCD's website under the event section and a number of stakeholders were also invited directly via emails. The registration for the event took place in the system that FBCD had at its disposal for events, this ensured documentation of the participation, name, emails and other information as well as the necessary consent for the use of contributions from the participation and images from this. FBCD's event system also ensures that a reminder email

is sent to all participants a few days before the event and that an evaluation form is sent to all participants the day after the event.

The workshop was also promoted via the newsletter FBCD sends out about upcoming events. AU also provided facilities for catering during the event.

3.2.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented

3.2.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note-taker etc.)
Michael Støckler - FBCD	Facilitator – Speaker, Note-taker
Mette Toft Christensen	Note-taker
Knud Tybirk - FBCD	Facilitator, speaker, recorder
Liselotte Puggaard – FBCD	Note-taker
Henrik B. Møller - AU	Speaker, tech support
Bruno Sander Nielsen - BG	Speaker

3.2.2.2 Participants

Participants list ¹		
Organisation	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
Biogas Danmark	Academia/Research	Biogas association
Aarhus University	Academia/Research	Researcher
Lundsby Renewable Solutions A/S	Industry	Turnkey provider biogas plants
Holstebro Struer Landboforening	Academia/Researcher	Advisory service for farmers
Nordic Green Engineering	Industry	Advisory service

¹ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

Geeen Island Vecycle ApS	Industry	Advisory service, equipment provider
Green Farm	Industry	Turnkey provider biogas plants
Green Farm	Industry	Turnkey provider biogas plants
Kuhr Hedegaard I/S	Industry	Farmer, biogas plant owner
Niras	Academia/Research	Biogas advisor
Sustaianble Bio Solutions Aabenraa K/S	Industry	Biogas plant owner, advisor
Stiesdal SkyClean	Industry	Researcher, plant provider
Lundsby Renewable Solutions A/S	Industry	Turnkey provider biogas plants
Lundsby Renewable Solutions A/S	Industry	Turnkey provider biogas plants
Aarhus University	Academia/Research	Biogas research
Fremsyn	Academia/Research	Advisory services
PurFil	Industry	Equipment provider
Nordic Green Engineering ApS	Industry	Advisory services
Disruptive Bio Trading ApS	Industry	Biomass trader
Agro Gas/BHJ A/S	Industry	Equipment provider
Green Iland Vecycle APs	Academia/Research	Advisory service
Nordic Green Engineering ApS	Industry	Advisory service

3.2.3 Detailed remarks

The session's comments and contributions have been categorized into three distinct sections: a concise overview of posts related to research activities in Denmark, a summary on the discussions of the political landscape for the biogas sector, and a comprehensive compilation encompassing all the valuable inputs provided by the participants.

The ongoing research efforts in the field of biogas production in Denmark are organized into the following themes:

- Climate and sustainability;
- Biomass and energy;
- Nutrient utilization and ecology.

In the realm of climate and sustainability, AU is deeply engaged in a multifaceted approach aimed at fostering a greener future. Their efforts encompass various critical areas that collectively contribute to mitigating environmental impacts and promoting sustainable practices including residence time, reduced emissions from facilities and storage, biomass selection, heat exchange, Power2x and CO₂ storage.

Within the Danish biomass and energy domain, work is centered on advancing the utilization of renewable resources for energy production. This encompasses:

- Increased straw-rich products;
- Clover grass and biorefining;
- Pyrolysis.

Finally, in the realm of nutrient utilization and ecology, AU's initiatives include reduced ammonia evaporation, better utilization of nitrogen (N), utilization of clover grass and fertilizer products and N₂ application (enrichment with N through the use of electricity).

Overall, there has been a major shift in the use of biomass for biogas production in recent years. The adoption of deep litter, straw, and industrial waste has witnessed substantial growth. Among the noteworthy resources viable for biogas production in Denmark, straw continues to hold considerable potential. Numerous experimental trials are currently underway, aiming to refine the treatment of straw to maximize its yield, whereas many large-scale plants have embraced straw as a valuable input. Additionally, wet straw stands out as an advantageous option for utilization. Concurrently, efforts are directed towards understanding the interplay between the biorefining of green biomass and the application of its derived juices for the ensiling of straw.

In terms of biomass, the character of the degassed biomass undergoes alteration, prompting a requirement for an extended residence time within biogas facilities due to shifts in biomass composition. This change leads to a notable increase in the dry matter content within bioreactors, reaching elevated levels in specific areas, affecting both pumpability and stirring dynamics. Prolonging the retention period can result in advantageous economic consequences. Additionally, modifications in the viscosity of the degassed biomass play a crucial role in nutrient leaching and the subsequent evaporation of ammonia.

Concerning technologies, various types of technologies are currently being tested to reduce ammonia volatilization including ultrasonic, electrokinetic, fractionation, field application, decanters, screw press and nitrogen enrichment using current. As we look ahead, the division of degassed biomass might become a requisite to lower its dry matter content. From now on, the dry matter content in the liquid fraction for application must be reduced to 3.6%. A promising technology for handling the fibre fraction is pyrolysis.

Regarding political engagement, Biogas Danmark operates as a membership association for individuals vested in biogas. The objective is to advance biogas production and utilization, foster circular economy principles, and facilitate the exchange of knowledge and expertise.

On the whole, the biogas sector in Denmark has undergone tremendous development since the energy settlement in 2012, where financial support for the production of biogas was adopted. Biogas production in Denmark now accounts for more than 30% of total Danish gas consumption, and most of the biogas comes from biogas plants based on livestock manure.

The majority of the biomass used in the biogas plants comes from slurry and solid manure from livestock production. A significant part of gas production comes from biomass with a higher energy content such as straw and industrial products.

The Danish gas grid represents the largest opportunity to store renewable energy. The proportion of biogas that is upgraded and used via the gas network is increasing dramatically. It is expected that the entire Danish gas consumption can be covered by biogas production in 2030. If planned tender rounds are implemented, a 100% supply with biogas can probably be achieved in 2027.

The current focal points in Denmark encompass national climate and energy targets, expediting biogas supply, setting ambitious CO₂ displacement criteria, and transitioning to unsupported production driven by market dynamics. Additionally, measures to regulate methane loss are being addressed. Financially, efforts are underway to establish a standardized CO₂ tax, provide tax exemptions for biogas injected into the gas network, and offer tax refunds for degassed livestock manure. Furthermore, it's imperative to ensure that the grid companies possess the capacity to manage the produced gas. This entails working on mechanisms such as guarantees of origin and exploring opportunities for trading liquid biogas internationally. The evolved characteristics of the degassed biomass necessitate novel legislative measures. Overall, despite Denmark's size, the nation stands as a pioneer in terms of the proportion of biogas in its gas supply.

3.2.3.1 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

Table 7. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Denmark categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of market features Clarification of CO₂ taxes Improved cooperation between parties Lack of competent labour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limit driving with biomass Optimizing logistics Financial security for production Political strategy Processing time with the authorities Lack of high-energy biomasses Methane release Habitual thinking Residual gas potential in decayed biomass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on odour Agriculture's best friend Local projects Local ownership Total solutions as a goal Focus on communication Focus on information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No recommendations provided
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector coupling Support for the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Faster case processing Political decision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update of the biogas manual Train the workforce Capacity-building programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common EU regulatory framework

	administrative path <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support and consulting • Financial security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance support • Business modelling and planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness-raising campaigns 	
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3.2.3.2 Final ranking: Top recommendations

The last part of the workshop provided room for discussion, recommendations and proposals. The following recommendations were provided by the participants:

- It is important to establish cooperation between the public and private sectors.
- It is important to create good neighbourly relations.
- There must be a focus on the challenges with odour.
- Acceptance must be created in the local community.
- It is important to optimize logistics and limit the transport of biomass.
- Greater cohesion must be created between energy production and agriculture.
- It must be ensured that there is sufficient biomass with a high energy content.
- A national strategy for the use of biomass must be drawn up.
- Financial security must be created for several years in order to secure investments.
- The utilization of the degassed biomass must be optimized.
- The processing time at the authorities' side must be reduced.
- A political decision must be made on the tax conditions for CO₂.
- More educational offers targeted at the biogas industry must be established, since there is a shortage of qualified labour.
- The focus must be on reducing methane emissions.
- There is a need for greater knowledge sharing between the biogas plants.
- The possibility of exporting biogas to the whole of Europe must be established.
- Synergies must be established for the upcoming Power2x technologies.
- An online platform for sharing information and collaboration, currently lacking, should be set up.
- The biogas process must continue to be optimized to increase efficiency.
- There will be a need for extensive trade in different biomasses.
- Separation of the degassed biomass may become necessary.
- Pyrolysis can become an option for handling the fibre fraction.
- CO₂ from the biogas plants will soon become a commodity.
- Experience and the exchange of knowledge must prevent wrong investments.
- There is a need for a platform that collects GIS data for agriculture and makes it available.
- There is a need to update the handbook for biogas establishment.
- There is a desire for a facility for sharing success and failure stories.
- It must be ensured that the grid companies can purchase the biogas produced.

The identified barriers and the recommendations put forth by the participants collectively underscore the multifaceted landscape of biogas production and its challenges. The barriers, ranging from regulatory uncertainties to resource limitations, pose significant hurdles that necessitate comprehensive solutions. The recommendations, on the other hand, emphasize the critical need for collaboration, community engagement, and strategic planning. It's evident that establishing a conducive environment for the biogas sector demands the synchronization of efforts across various domains, including policy formulation, technological innovation, and knowledge sharing. The call for financial stability, educational programmes, optimized logistics, and a strategic approach to biomass utilization highlights the interconnectedness of these challenges and the importance of a holistic

approach. By acknowledging the potential of emerging technologies like Power2x and exploring options like pyrolysis, the biogas industry must commit to continuous improvement and adaptation.

In parallel, the identified needs collectively underline a comprehensive roadmap for the future of the biogas industry in Denmark. The recognition of sector coupling, along with the significance of administrative support and technical guidance, underscores the importance of a collaborative approach encompassing both public and private sectors. Mitigating challenges like odour, promoting community acceptance, and optimizing logistics are pivotal to creating harmonious coexistence. The call for a national biomass strategy and financial security highlights the need for proactive policies and stable investment environments. Furthermore, as the industry embraces advancements like Power2x technologies and pyrolysis, fostering synergy and innovation will be paramount. Sharing knowledge, facilitating learning, and leveraging emerging technologies are essential to enhance efficiency, reduce emissions, and open avenues for biogas trade on a larger scale.

Additionally, it's worth noting that specific services were not extensively discussed separately; however, the presented recommendations were collectively validated by the participants, reflecting their relevance and potential effectiveness in addressing the identified challenges. Furthermore, it's important to highlight that while specific services were not extensively discussed, it's notable that raising awareness among citizens in Denmark was not deemed to be as crucial a priority compared to other types of support measures.

In terms of support services, it becomes evident that the participants overall agreed that the services offered by the project are equally important and appeared to be particularly interested in fostering a knowledge-sharing ecosystem. They articulated a strong desire for a dedicated platform that facilitates the exchange of information about biogas production, showcasing both best practices and lessons learned from real-world experiences. The emphasis on creating forums for process optimization and the sharing of successes and challenges further underscores the commitment to advancing biogas technology collectively. Participants further emphasized on the importance of good neighbourly relations and addressing challenges with odour aligns with the aspiration for information campaigns targeted at authorities and neighbours, indicating a holistic approach to community engagement.

Additionally, the workshop's participants highlighted the importance of innovation in feedstock utilization. The interest in information on new types of biomass that can be utilized for biogas production reflects a forward-looking mindset within the industry, aiming to diversify and enhance the efficiency of biogas generation. At the same time, the regulatory landscape was not overlooked, as participants emphasized the need for streamlined EU regulations that account for environmental impacts and safety concerns. Geographical aspects were another prominent theme, with calls for GIS data platforms and location-based information in line with the need for optimizing logistics and limiting biomass transport to facilitate efficient biomass utilization.

Education emerged also as a cornerstone of the recommended support for biogas adoption. The need for updated educational resources, training opportunities for employees, and the establishment of educational programs reflects a holistic approach to knowledge dissemination and skills development, ensuring the long-term viability of biogas solutions. Furthermore, the emphasis on experience sharing through case databases and peer groups signals a collaborative spirit, whereas establishing an online resource catalogue for challenges and solutions, as well as a knowledge bank on biomass, underlines the need for accessible information and continuous learning.

3.2.4 *Communication and Dissemination*

To ensure awareness and participation, we implemented several actions to promote the workshop:

- ✓ **Dissemination via targeted e-mails:** FBCD has an extensive member database and this was used to select a group of biogas stakeholders who were sent a direct invitation to participate in the workshop. Direct emails to people you already know are very effective for events recruitment.
- ✓ **Dissemination on project's social media:** FBCD actively shared information and updates about the workshop on social media channels (LinkedIn). This allowed to reach a larger audience and generate interest among individuals following the project's online presence.
- ✓ **Dissemination via the FBCD website:** FBCD has an independent section of the website where upcoming events are promoted. The cocreation workshop was promoted via this section, as presented in the following picture.

Figure 6. Example of website post for the Danish workshop

- ✓ **Dissemination via FBCD newsletters:** FBCD sends out a specialized newsletter where upcoming events are presented. The workshop has thus been presented through this medium to all subscribers and members of FBCD.

A reminder email was sent to all registrants two days before the event.

3.2.5 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

During the workshop, notes were collected from all participants in three consecutive record sessions. The collected posts were systematized and photographed for later documentation. Pictures were taken in connection with the workshop and pictures were taken in connection with the inspection of the biogas plant.

Figure 7. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Denmark

3.3 Co-creation Workshop in Greece

3.3.1 Workshop's general information

On Wednesday 28th of June 2023, the co-creation workshop for the Greek ALFA Hub, titled "Co-design solutions to increase biogas production from animal waste" took place from 12:00 to 13:45 EEST. The event was conducted via MS Teams and was organized by Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC, with support by CERTH. Overall, a total of 35 participants registered for it. However, only 16 external participants attended.

The methodology for the event consisted of two sessions. The first session focused on the validation and prioritization of the regional barriers and needs following the CHML methodology, while the second session involved the development of support plans via an open panel discussion.

Apart from the common agenda and slides provided by WR, the content of the event primarily followed the instructions and format set by WR. Additionally, during the closing session, two relevant projects named CO2SMOS and BIOMETHAVERSE were presented by CERTH.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

The Greek ALFA Hub, managed by Q-PLAN, taking into consideration the location of our partner CERTH (who actively supported the Greek co-creation workshop – CCW), and the busy schedules of our local partners, opted for the online format. Furthermore, the scheduling was also carefully considered and discussed both with CERTH and various local partners to ensure their availability, with the twin goals of representative participation and effectiveness on CCW's results with active participation in co-creation sessions.

Following the guidelines of WR, the Greek CCW was organised by Q-PLAN International with the support of CERTH and took place on the 28th of June 2023 at 12.00 - 13.45. The online platform selected for hosting the CCW was MS Teams, a tool which offers satisfactory meeting management, seamless communication, and real time collaboration, whilst is familiar to most local actors contacted during the previous period. Apart from the above-mentioned advantages, MS Teams was selected because of its security requirements, its flexibility, and the user-friendly interface.

Q-PLAN prepared the official invitation and the agenda of the CCW, and shared it with CERTH, in order both to invite local partners, either via telephone and/or e-mails in the livestock sector and/or biogas sector, academics, researchers, associations, civil society organisations covering the whole spectrum of the Quadruple Helix, already part of the local ALFA network established. In total 35 participants registered to the event in a short period that were representative of the stakeholders required, albeit for reasons of transparency further dissemination actions were pursued, esp. in the social media.

A couple of days before the CCW, Q-PLAN sent an e-mail with a link to join the CCW to the registered members. In total, 24 people attended the CCW and actively participated throughout its duration. In order to attract and disseminate the event Q-PLAN created posts through its official social media accounts on the 26th of June 2023 that were reposted and circulated among its SMA followers and networks. Additionally, Q-PLAN circulated an email invitation to its relevant networks and in particular to the contacts already established during the WP1 interviews.

With the aim of building and maintaining concrete collaborations and synergies, during the workshop two similar projects were invited to be presented by CERTH, named [CO2SMOS](#) and [BIOMETHAVERSE](#), which kicked off a framework of close collaboration between them.

The event announcement was posted at HABIO's (Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers) website. After the completion of the workshop, Q-PLAN shared the materials of the workshop with the participants (the presentation of the ALFA project, the needs and barriers, the successful cases and the support services, the Mentimeter results and the prioritization of them, the Miro board with the feedback on services along with the brief presentation of CO2SMOS and BIOMETHAVERSE projects) and gave the opportunity to participants to express any further idea and feedback.

3.3.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented

3.3.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role
Ioannis Konstas – Q-PLAN	Facilitator
Andromachi Kalaouzi – Q-PLAN	Presenter, Tech support
Kostas Dasopoulos – Q-PLAN	Support - Expert
Prodromos Gkalimanis – Q-PLAN	Support - Expert

3.3.2.2 Participants

Participants list ³		
Organisation	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
Βιοαέριο Αυλίδος IKE, [translation Biogas Avlidos]	Industry	Biogas Plant manager
Freelancer Engineer	Industry	Environmental Engineer, Biogas Plant Authorisation Expert
Engineer for Business	Industry	Business Advisor
Argyropoulos S.A.	Industry	Environmental Engineer
DUTH	Academia/Research	Postgraduate Student Environmental Engineering
DUTH	Academia/Research	Postgraduate Student of Environmental Engineering
EDA THESS	Industry	Gas Distributor Company, Thessaloniki - Thessalia

³ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

EDA THESS	Industry	Gas Distributor Company, Thessaloniki - Thessalia
IDEP	Academia/Research	Researcher
DUTH	Academia/Research	Academic
Engineer for Business	Industry	Business Advisor
CBS	Academia/Research	Academic
Biogas professional	Industry	Business Executive
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	Farmer/Biomass producer
QLAB	Industry	Research & analytical laboratory
HABIO (Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers)	Industry	Representative of Hellenic Biogas Association

3.3.3 Detailed remarks from Session 1

3.3.3.1 List of recommendations presented to the participants

Barriers	Needs
Technical Barriers: Lack of gas grid, Technical constraints for collecting manure	Technical Support Needs: Technical support and consultation, Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions
Business/administrative Barriers: High investment costs, Lack of financial support, Limited investment access, Uncertain and unsupportive policy framework, Complexity of the administrative and legislative framework, Lack of know-how for biogas projects	Business/Admin Support Needs: Access to finance support, Raising awareness to overcome locals' opposition, Administrative support during licensing process
Social barriers: Low social acceptance	Awareness-raising and capacity-building activities: Awareness-raising campaigns, Capacity-building programmes

3.3.3.2 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

During the first part of the CCW, the coordinator of ALFA and event Facilitator welcomed the participants and expressed his gratitude for taking the time to participate in the event. During the

introductory session of the CCW, the consortium, the main objectives, the expected results and the impact of the ALFA project, with special focus on the role of ALFA Hubs, were presented to the participants by I. Konstas and A. Kalaouzi.

After the presentations, participants had short Q & A sessions to learn more about the co-creation workshop, and to receive information about the project and its future activities that they could join. With a focus on Greece, Q-PLAN presented the analysis results from the early stages of ALFA project. They revealed the barriers, the needs and the enablers at EU level and in Greece. The session also included three successful cases in Greece and their success factors.

After that, the facilitator demonstrated Mentimeter as an online tool, and invited the participants to group and rank the barriers and the needs identified by the ALFA analysis results. The outcomes are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Greece categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of policy implementation despite its enactment • Absence of a clear framework for biomethane production • Efficient management of large amounts of digested residue • Uncertain and unsupportive policy framework • High initial investment costs • Lack of financial support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of the administrative and legislative framework (licensing) • Investment access • Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of gas grid • Technical constrains for collecting manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low social acceptance
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper processing of digestate • Incentives, in order digestate to return as fertiliser to producers. • Quality control is essential for both the raw material (e.g. manure) and the by-product (i.e. digestate used as fertiliser). • Capacity building about the circular economy concept and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising campaigns • Technical support and consultation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative support during authorization process • Support to overcome local's opposition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building programmes

	<p>how biogas is closely related to it, not only for farmers and livestock farmers but also for the wider community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance support • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of the biogas solutions 			
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3.3.3.3 Interactive Session 1 – Additional priorities provided by participants

Based on the abovementioned needs and barriers as discussed during the workshop, the following additional priorities were provided by the attendees:

- The challenge of managing the large amounts of digested residue that could be used as fertilizer;
- The lack of policy implementation despite its enactment, and the absence of a clear framework for biomethane production;
- Proper processing of digestate is needed to enable its year-round use and to incentivize its return to the raw material producers;
- Quality control is essential for both the raw material (e.g. manure) as well as the by-product (i.e. digestate used as fertiliser);
- Capacity building about the circular economy concept is a top priority, as biogas is closely related to it, not only for farmers and livestock farmers in local communities but for the wider community, as well.

3.3.3.4 Interactive Session 1 – Final ranking: Top recommendations

- **Business support:**
 1. Access to finance;
 2. Lack of financial support.
- **Technical support:**
 1. Proper processing of digestate;
 2. Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of the biogas solutions.
- **Awareness-raising** about incentives, in order for the digestate to return as fertiliser to producers.
- **Capacity-building** about the circular economy concept and how biogas is closely related to it, not only for farmers and livestock farmers but also in local communities.

3.3.4 Detailed remarks from Session 2

3.3.4.1 Business/Financial Services - Support Plan

During the discussions on business and financial support services, several main remarks were brought up by the participants. One significant point of interest was the **need for improved access to finance** in the biogas sector. Participants recognized the importance of this service and emphasized its necessity.

Another suggestion raised during the discussions was the possibility of **expanding the farmer-to-farmer service to include business-related aspects**. Drawing from the successful format of the farmer-to-farmer service, participants proposed its implementation from biogas plant to biogas plant, thereby facilitating knowledge and experience sharing among industry stakeholders.

To promote greater gender diversity and inclusion, participants suggested **directly inviting women to participate in open calls** or actively promoting female participation in the biogas sector. Encouraging women's involvement in the industry was seen as a valuable step toward fostering a more inclusive and diverse community.

Recognizing **the influential role of local livestock associations**, participants highlighted their potential as key players in the engagement process between interested farms and biogas plants. Leveraging the connections and resources of these associations could facilitate smoother collaborations and enhance the growth of the biogas sector at a local level.

Table 9. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Greece

<i>Business/Financial Support Services Support Plan - GR</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Farmer-to-farmer
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The farmer-to-farmer service could be moved to the business services • Based on the format of farmer-to-farmer service, could be implemented from biogas plant to biogas plant • Actively invite and promote female participation in the biogas sector • Foster partnerships and collaborations with local livestock associations to support biogas initiatives.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

3.3.4.2 Technical Services - Support Plan

During the discussions on technical support services, several main remarks were raised by the participants. One suggestion put forward was to **expand the farmer-to-farmer service to encompass business services as well**. Participants recognized the potential value of leveraging the existing framework of the farmer-to-farmer service to provide additional support in business-related aspects of the biogas sector.

Among the technical support services, the **consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions** emerged as particularly intriguing to the participants. This service was deemed essential for ensuring the successful implementation and ongoing operation of biogas projects. The expertise and guidance provided by consultants in this area were seen as crucial for addressing technical challenges and optimizing system performance.

Considering the geographical distances between technical partners and beneficiaries, participants recommended the **use of remote meetings**. This approach would overcome the logistical challenges posed by the partners being located in urban areas like Athens, Greece, while the beneficiaries were situated in rural areas. Remote meetings were seen as an effective means to bridge the gap, enabling efficient communication and collaboration between technical experts and project stakeholders.

Table 10. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Greece

<i>Technical Support Services Support Plan - GR</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas plants • Remote meetings for efficient communication between technical partners and beneficiaries.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate business-related support into existing farmer-to-farmer service platforms • Participants recommended remote meetings since the technical partners are located away (i.e. for Greece technical partners are located in Athens and the beneficiaries in rural areas).
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

3.3.4.3 Awareness-raising activities - Support Plan

During the discussions on awareness raising activities, several main remarks were highlighted by the participants. One significant observation was the **lack of sufficient information available regarding the proper use of digestate**. Participants emphasized the need for increased awareness and knowledge on how to utilize digestate effectively, considering its importance in the biogas sector.

Another notable point raised during the discussions was the **general lack of awareness regarding the concept of bioeconomy and its connection to livestock residues and biogas**. Participants identified a **need for educational efforts** to promote understanding and recognition of how these elements play a vital role in the broader bioeconomy framework.

Participants also mentioned an **ongoing campaign between HABIO and the European Biogas Association (EBA)** aimed at raising public awareness. They suggested leveraging this existing campaign to further address the identified gaps and expand the outreach efforts. By utilizing the campaign's existing channels and resources, such as social media or educational materials, the awareness raising activities could be optimized to reach a broader audience and bridge the knowledge gaps in the biogas sector.

Table 11. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Greece

<i>Awareness-raising Activities Support Plan - GR</i>	
Type of awareness-raising activities required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Potential topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Proper use of digestate → Bioeconomy development and utilization of livestock residues.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging existing awareness campaigns to expand outreach efforts (e.g. there is already a campaign between HABIO and EBA in order to increase public awareness) • Develop targeted educational materials and resources on digestate utilization and the bioeconomy • Utilize various communication channels, including social media, websites, and workshops, to disseminate information effectively.
Messages to focus on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance and proper utilization of digestate in the biogas sector. • Role of livestock residues and biogas in the broader bioeconomy framework. • Benefits of biogas production for sustainable agriculture and waste management.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Farmers • Researchers
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

3.3.4.4 Capacity-building programmes - Support Plan

During the discussions on capacity building activities, several main remarks were brought up by the participants. One suggested topic for capacity building was exploring the connection between biogas production and the circular economy. Participants recognized the potential for **highlighting the role of biogas in promoting a circular economy** and the benefits it brings to sustainable resource management.

Another topic of interest was finding ways to **engage more women in biogas production within the livestock sector**. Participants recognized the importance of promoting gender diversity and inclusivity in the biogas industry and discussed potential strategies for encouraging women's participation and representation.

Among the various topics discussed, **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** emerged as the most intriguing to the participants. LCA provides a comprehensive analysis of the environmental impact of biogas production and utilization, and participants recognized its value in promoting sustainable practices and decision-making.

Considering the Greek context, participants suggested that capacity-building seminars should be conducted in Greek to cater to the Greek Hub. They also proposed **collaborating with the livestock farmers association** to ensure effective outreach and engagement with the target audience.

Additionally, to promote the benefits of digestate as fertilizer, participants highlighted the importance of involving agronomists in capacity-building activities. **Agronomists were recognized as influential figures among farmers**, and their support and endorsement could significantly contribute to the adoption of digestate as a valuable fertilizer.

Furthermore, participants emphasized the **need to target biogas facilities and livestock farm managers** to integrate gender mainstreaming into plant activities. By incorporating gender considerations into management practices, participants believed that greater gender equality and inclusivity could be achieved within the biogas industry.

Table 12. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Greece

<i>Capacity-building Programmes Support Plan - GR</i>	
Type of capacity-building programmes required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Potential topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Biogas and the circular economy → Women engagement in biogas production in the livestock industry → Training on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for environmental impact analysis.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct capacity-building seminars in the local language to enhance accessibility and engagement • Collaborate with livestock farmers associations to ensure effective outreach and participation • Involve agronomists in capacity-building activities to promote the benefits of digestate as fertilizer • Incorporate gender considerations and mainstreaming into plant activities and management practices.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational materials on circular economy, LCA, and digestate utilization • Expert trainers and facilitators • Collaboration with livestock farmers associations and agronomists for outreach and support.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agronomists • Farmers • Managers of biogas facilities/livestock farms.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

3.3.5 Closing session

As already referred above, during the closing session, two projects were presented that have strong links with ALFA. One is called [CO2SMOS](#) (Solutions for a circular bio-based industry) and the other

BIOMETHAVERSE (demonstrating and connecting production innovations in the biomethane universe). Both projects were presented by experts from CERTH.

The project coordinator thanked the participants for their active involvement and encouraged them to keep in touch and follow ALFA activities, as the ALFA Engagement Platform and Decision Support Tools will be online soon. Participants showed their interest in future collaboration with the project, while Advisory Board members highlighted the value of such initiatives to foster the shift to renewable energy and a more efficient primary sector.

3.3.6 Communication and Dissemination

A social media post prepared and posted on official social accounts of Q-PLAN, in order to promote the event. The social media post was uploaded on 26th of June at [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and its designed was based on the banner prepared by WR. The posts are depicted below. The announcement of the event was also posted on the [website](#) of HABIO on June 1st 2023.

3.3.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Figure 8. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Greece

3.4 Co-creation Workshop in Italy

3.4.1 Workshop's general information

On July 11th, 2023, the Italian ALFA Co-creation Workshop took place. The workshop was conducted online via the TEAMS platform following an open panel format and the event was organized by APRE and A0CO2, who successfully gathered a total of 15 participants in attendance. The workshop followed a common agenda and utilized slides that were provided by WR. The participants engaged in interactive discussions and activities guided by the CHML methodology to explore and generate ideas.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

A preliminary consultation was carried out by APRE and A0CO2 with CIB, the Italian Biogas Consortium. The CIB carried out a preliminary consultation with one of the CIB members, Riccardo Ferrero of La Falchetta Farm (already interviewed by APRE as best case), who later joined the workshop in order to ensure that the most important issues and needs for all the Italian Biogas Consortium were discussed. Furthermore, the Advisory Board Member Lorenzo Maggioni was consulted to validate the materials covered, which were all translated into Italian language to facilitate the understanding of the participants.

List of promoting actions:

- 1) Letter of invitation to participants
- 2) [Social Media post with sharing of official ALFA project page LinkedIn post \(LinkedIn\).](#)

3.4.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented

3.4.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note taker etc.)
Riccardo Coletta - APRE	Facilitator
Enrico Facci – A0CO2	Facilitator
Flaminia Rocca - APRE	Tech Support, Facilitator, Note taker
Alessandro Rosati – A0CO2	Note taker, Facilitator
Marco Regi - APRE	Note taker
Ilaria Bientinesi – A0CO2	Note taker

3.4.2.2 Participants list

Participants list ⁴		
Organisation	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
Sardegna Ricerche	Academia	Researcher on Bioenergy
University of Verona, Department of biotechnology	Academia / Research	Researcher on Biotechnology
ENEA, National agency for new technologies, energy and sustainable economic development	Academia / Government	Researcher on Bioenergy / Policy Consultant
La Falchetta Farm, CIB (Italian Biogas Consortium) member	Industry	Farmer with biogas plant
Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Biology and Biotechnology "C. Darwin"	Academia / Research	Researcher on Biotechnology

⁴ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

University of Tuscia	Academia / Research	Researcher on Bioenergy
Private Consultant	Industry	Senior Advisor, Biogas and Biomethane Expert / Advisory Board Member
ITABIA Italian Biomass Association	Civil Society	Non-profit association with focus on Bioenergy
CNR, National Research Centre	Academia / Research	Researcher on Bioenergy
CRPA, Research Centre on Animal Productions	Industry	Service provider
CNR ISPAAM, Institute for the Animal Production System in the Mediterranean Environment	Research	Researcher on Bioenergy
ARAL, Lombardy Regional Breeders Association	Civil Society	Breeders Trade Association
Order of engineers of Rome	Industry	Tech consultant
BIOELECTRIC NV	Industry	Biogas Plant Producer
S.Agostino Farm	Industry	Farmer with biogas plant

3.4.3 Detailed remarks from Session 1

The introductory session of the workshop was used to present the agenda of the co-creation workshop and the ALFA project, with a general overview of its characteristics, presented by Riccardo Coletta of APRE, as manager of the Italian HUB, with the material provided by WR. Some participants had already contributed to the preliminary analyses of the project, and already had some basic knowledge about our activities, while others were unaware of it and asked to receive the project presentation, as well as the link to the website. They were also suggested to follow ALFA's LinkedIn page.

When presenting the services, the participants took notes for the questions and suggestions they would like to propose in the development of the support plans, and asked if these services were in some way in conflict with those provided by the CIB, the Italian Biogas Consortium. They were told by Riccardo Coletta of APRE and Enrico Facci of A0CO2 that the Italian HUB had consulted with the CIB, (Consorzio Italiano Biogas) and that the services offered by ALFA are in ideal synergy and not in conflict with those offered by the latter.

The capacity buildings activities and possible topics were presented, too, together with the raising awareness campaigns objectives and a general overview on the monitoring and evaluation framework, whose structure were considered well planned, and whose indicators and questions were, instead, validated during the development of each of the intended support plans. The introductory phase of the workshop lasted, as planned in the agenda, about 40 minutes.

3.4.3.1 List of recommendations presented to the participants

Barriers	Needs
Technical Barriers: Lack of technical knowledge, Technical constraints for collecting manure	Technical Support Needs: Technical support and consulting, Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions, Concept design and development of biogas solutions, Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions
Business/administrative Barriers: High investment costs, Uncertain policy framework, Complex administrative and legal procedures	Business/Admin Support Needs: Financial assessment, Access to finance, Administrative support, Business modelling and planning
Social barriers: Lack of information, Low social acceptance	Awareness-raising and capacity-building activities: Awareness-raising activities and capacity-building programmes

3.4.3.2 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

In general, the workshop was rather particular in the use of the Mentimeter tool: the participants, probably because of a lack of familiarity with the instrument, proved to be rather uncertain in assigning a score to the barriers and needs, often giving a place in the middle of the ranking.

However, once the various barriers and needs had been entered on their respective boards, the participants agreed that they had assigned too low scores to the priority of some barriers and needs, which they then instead wanted to place, on the blackboard, in the categories "critical urgency" and "high urgency". The aforementioned disposition will be commented in the next paragraph.

Furthermore, topics that had been considered unimportant in the validation poll, such as social acceptance and the need for well-targeted awareness campaigns, were then taken up again in the debate during the second phase of co-creation, when it was agreed that, many of the obstacles reported above all by the farmers present, would be surmountable also thanks to an appropriate awareness campaign and dialogue with the local, national and European authorities, and the policy-makers in general. This issue will be further explained in paragraphs dedicated to the second co-creation phase.

As already anticipated above, the participants agreed that most of the barriers that emerged from the previous analyses of ALFA represented critical urgencies practically all on the same level. However, the ranking that resulted from the poll was, as regards the critical and high urgencies, the following: in first place, the **high investment costs**, in the second place the **uncertain and unsupportive regulatory framework**, in the third place the **administrative and legal procedures regarded as too complex**, the fourth the risks associated with the investment and the fifth the lack of financial support. The last places in the classification, with medium and low-level urgency, were occupied by poor social acceptance, lack of technical knowledge, lack of information and technical constraints for collecting manure. However, while this last barrier was considered not very relevant to the current condition of biogas in Italy and therefore was no longer the subject of discussion, the others were extensively taken up and re-evaluated in their criticality in the second phase of co-creation, in particular within the messages to be conveyed in awareness raising campaigns.

Furthermore, seeing the barriers reported on the Miro board, the participants, who expressed the desire to reformulate some opinions, agreed that the urgencies to be considered critical were: the uncertain regulatory framework, the high investment costs, the administrative procedures and complex legal issues, and poor coordination of the supply chain. However, the lack of financial support and technical knowledge, as well as the risk factor in investing in biogas, were chosen as high-urgency barriers.

Table 13. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Italy categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment costs • Uncertain policy framework • Complex administrative and legal procedures • Poor supply chain coordination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risks associated with the investment • Lack of financial support • Lack of technical knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of technical skills • Lack of information • Poor social acceptance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical constraints for collecting manure • Concerns about the sustainability of biogas plants
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial assessment • Access to finance • Administrative support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support and consulting • Business modelling and planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions • Concept design and development of biogas solutions • Awareness campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building programmes • Consultancy for the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions

The alignment between the order of importance of needs from the Mentimeter vote and their final representation on the Miro board was more congruent. However, participants reiterated that, in this instance as well, the needs up to the fifth place in the ranking held comparable significance, interconnected and mutually important.

The needs were ranked as follows, from most to the least critical: financial assessment, access to financial support, administrative support, technical support and consultancy, business modelling and planning, assessment of the potential of biogas solutions, concept design and development of biogas solutions, awareness campaigns, capacity building programmes, consultancy for the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions.

As can be seen, awareness-raising campaigns and capacity-building programmes, perhaps because they were general categories, were placed low in the ranking. However, as already mentioned, they played an important role in the subsequent debate, where many critical issues

emerged on which to sensitise policy-makers and citizens, and many topics on which to base a capacity building process.

3.4.3.3 Interactive Session 1 – Additional priorities provided by participants

In general, in this first session, the participants limited themselves to commenting on the proposed barriers (which, for Italy, included the poor coordination of the supply chain, a specific datum of the Italian Hub that emerged from the interviews and surveys carried out previously). However, during the second session, while developing the support plans, many barriers and specific needs included in the macro-themes presented on the boards emerged, and will be explained in this report in the session dedicated to the second phase of co-creation.

3.4.3.4 Interactive Session 1 – Final ranking: Top recommendations

- **Business support:**
 1. Financial Evaluation;
 2. Access to Financial Support;
 3. Administrative Support;
 4. Business Modelling and Planning.
- **Technical support:** Technical Support (and consultancy).
- **Awareness-raising:**
 1. High Investment Costs;
 2. Uncertain Policy Landscape;
 3. Unsupportive Regulatory Framework;
 4. Complex Administrative and Legal Procedure;
 5. Poor Supply Chain Coordination;
 6. Investment Risks.
- **Capacity-building:**
 1. Lack of technical knowledge and Infrastructure;
 2. Access to Financial Support;
 3. Poor Supply Chain Coordination.

3.4.4 Detailed remarks from Session 2

Despite all participants being experts in the bioenergy sector, the workshop had a considerable number of attendees, totalling 15 participants (excluding moderators). APRE and A0CO2 chose an open panel format in response to the participants' expressed desire for a collective debate. Many of the present interlocutors held prominent positions within the Italian biogas landscape, making the open panel format suitable for facilitating meaningful discussions. All four expected topics have been addressed, and a support plan has been duly compiled. As regards the validation of the monitoring and evaluation framework, the participants reported all indicators already evaluated by the previous analyses of the ALFA project, without adding particular inputs. In general, the participants complimented the meeting and the ability, in a short time, to condense all the most critical points inherent to the biogas situation in Italy. As we will see, conflicting opinions concerning the future of

biofuels in Italy were expressed by the various participants, based on their own experiences and skills. However, all the arguments turned out to be valid and well thought out, a symptom that in Italy the perspective on the future is quite uneven, despite all the participants having validated the priorities and the needs proposed, albeit experienced and faced in different ways.

3.4.4.1 Business/Financial Services - Support Plan

During the discussions, the participants identified the business services that were deemed most suitable for meeting their needs. These business services included **market research, access to finance, and corporate and sustainable finance**. However, it was observed that **business modelling and planning** was not specifically mentioned in the initial discussions, but it was frequently referred to later on during the debate. This suggests that the latter service can be considered validated and relevant to the participants' needs.

The invited farmers highlighted the importance of **integrating the business modelling and planning service specifically in the context of biomethane**, which is seen as a promising future perspective for those who already have biogas facilities in Italy. They emphasized that a comprehensive business plan is necessary for those considering the upgrade to biomethane, including realistic costs associated with grid connection. Currently, the biomethane plants face closure due to excessively high connection costs. Additionally, there is a need to have a clear understanding of the biomass procurement costs for the next 15 years in order to ensure the viability of biomethane projects. These costs must be accessible and manageable for the industry to thrive.

Table 14. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Italy

<i>Business/Financial Support Services Support Plan - IT</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Research • Access to finance support • Corporate and Sustainable Finance • Business Modelling and Planning
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of the business modelling and planning service is crucial in the context of biomethane • Encourage aggregation of farmers to increase the size and capacity of biomethane plants • Promote inter-company plants from a financial perspective • Integrate business modelling and planning service with consideration for linking plant size to company characteristics • Provide an overview of various financing methods for the access to finance support service • Requested implementation of a decision support service.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

In addition to the previous points, it was suggested that **a service should be provided to encourage the aggregation of farmers**, aiming to increase the size and capacity of the biomethane plants. When discussing the technical and logistical challenges of transporting livestock manure, it was mentioned that selecting areas where farms are situated close to each other would eliminate the need for extensive transportation of manure over long distances. This approach would alleviate the associated logistical concerns. Furthermore, it was emphasized that from a financial perspective, **supporting inter-company plants should be prioritized to maximize their viability and success**.

Farmers emphasized the importance of integrating the Business Modelling and Planning service with a specific focus on linking the size of the biomethane plants to the characteristics of each individual company. This integration should consider factors such as substrate production capacity, financial capabilities, and managerial expertise. It was suggested that the biomethane plant should operate within the farm in a circular economy system, promoting sustainability and resource efficiency.

Regarding the **access to finance** service, it was highlighted that a comprehensive understanding of the various financing methods available is crucial. Farmers expressed the **need for an overview of different funding options** to make informed decisions about securing financial support for their biomethane projects.

Additionally, participants requested the provision of a **decision support service**. This service would assist farmers in making well-informed choices by providing relevant information, analysis, and guidance throughout the decision-making process related to biomethane production and related activities.

3.4.4.2 Technical Services - Support Plan

During the discussions, it was noted that biogas is a versatile energy source, suitable for both large and small farms. Therefore, the services offered by ALFA were considered applicable to all types of users.

Additionally, private bioenergy business consultants suggested removing the **concept design and development of biogas systems** service, as it was viewed as a task carried out by specialized technicians and companies rather than a consultancy service. However, another opinion was expressed, advocating for the **integration and focus of concept design and development of biogas systems service on preliminary feasibility studies** that would assist farmers in making informed decisions.

Table 15. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Italy

<i>Technical Support Services Support Plan - IT</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept design and development of biogas systems • Evaluation of biogas potential based on preliminary calculations • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions (including operation and maintenance training) • Evaluation and comparison of plant suppliers' quotes • Farmer-to-farmer advice
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The services offered by ALFA can be suitable for all types of users • Private bioenergy business consultants recommended removing the Concept design and development of biogas systems service, as it is not a consultancy service and is typically handled by specialized

	<p>technicians and companies in the sector. In contrary, some attendees suggested keeping and adjusting the service, with a focus on integrating it with preliminary feasibility studies assisting farmers in making informed choices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowing the Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) of biomass is crucial for the Concept design and development service, which involves evaluating biogas potential based on preliminary calculations • There is a need for professional technical training services focused on biomass, optimizing fermentation processes, and valorising fermentative intermediates and waste. This training is required for farmers as well as professionals in the sector, including biologists and chemical engineers.
<p>Impact Evaluation - Questions</p>	<p>Nothing extra was added.</p>

Regarding the evaluation of biogas potential based on preliminary calculations, participants emphasized the importance of knowing the Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) of biomass as a crucial factor in the evaluation process.

Furthermore, there was a consensus on the **need for professional technical training services related to biomass**, optimizing fermentation processes, and valorising fermentative intermediates and waste. These training programs were considered essential for farmers and individuals in the sector, such as biologists and chemical engineers, to enhance their expertise in these areas.

Additionally, there is a recognized **need for a professional technical training service that covers various aspects related to biomass utilization**. This training should encompass areas such as optimizing fermentation processes, the valorisation of fermentative intermediates and waste, and other relevant topics. Such training is crucial for farmers and industry professionals, including biologists and chemical engineers, as it equips them with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively work with biomass, enhance fermentation processes, and maximize the value obtained from fermentative byproducts and waste materials.

3.4.4.3 Awareness-raising activities - Support Plan

Depending on the stakeholder group of the participants, a variety of opinions were raised on the awareness-raising activities required.

According to the service providers, **a political lobbying process is needed to raise awareness** on several points: a) not to exclude electric biogas from Italy's future prospects, and, on the contrary, restore the incentives for electricity production with biogas, at least for plants that are far from the grid of natural gas and cannot connect or for those too small to upgrade; b) forcing the gas network operators to grant the connection of plants also in the peripheral branches of the grid itself; c) update the legislation on energy communities to also allow old plants to be part of them, and also encourage the sharing of heat and methane gas, not just electricity; d) streamline the bureaucratic process for connection to the biomethane grids, where possible.

On one hand, **the farmers emphasize the importance of raising awareness among authorities to expand the scope of regulations and incentive schemes**. They advocate for a broader application of these measures to support the development of the biogas sector.

On the other hand, **biogas plant owners contend that addressing social protests requires providing accurate information about the actual impact of small electric biogas plants.** These smaller-scale plants are more feasible for the majority of Italian farms, especially small and medium-sized ones. They caution against promoting the aggregation of farms to opt for biomethane, as it would lead to increased protests due to the continuous traffic of agricultural vehicles, tankers, and trucks required for transporting manure and livestock waste, leading to elevated pollution and noise levels in the affected areas.

Table 16. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Italy

<i>Awareness-raising Activities Support Plan - IT</i>	
Type of awareness-raising activities required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information campaigns with a specific target in Southern Italy
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase awareness among authorities about the need to expand regulations and incentives Provide correct information about the impact of small electric biogas plants to address social protests Conduct information campaigns targeting Southern Italy to educate citizens about biogas advantages Promote participation in synergies and consortia like the Italian Biogas Consortium Foster collaboration with other European projects and share experiences and research
Messages to focus on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The benefits of electricity production with biogas The impact of small electric biogas plants to address social protests
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residents of Southern Italy
Impact Evaluation - Questions	Nothing extra was added.

In terms of target groups, participants suggested that the information campaigns should target Southern Italy specifically, where citizens are generally poorly informed or totally uninformed about the advantages of biogas, both at an economic level for the local fabric and at a sustainability level.

Moreover, it was highlighted that **the authorities need to become aware of the importance of providing farmers with a long-term remunerative economic framework** that guarantees earnings taking inflation into account. Several participants suggested focusing awareness campaigns on the importance of farmers being part of chains of synergies and consortia, such as the Italian Biogas Consortium (CIB).

Additionally, participants noted that **policy-makers have to be reminded of the need for policy intervention to broaden the mentality**, for example through the implementation of regulations with progressive incentives to create energy cooperatives. It was also deemed necessary to inform policy-makers about the importance of introducing concepts related to renewable energies, including

biogas, into school courses to ensure future generations are knowledgeable about these topics. At the same time, it was emphasized that both farmers and policy-makers should not exclusively focus on biomethane but should continue to promote the adoption and diffusion of electric biogas.

Regarding biomethane upgrading, farmers faced challenges related to the timing of investments and lengthy permit processes. Incentive regulations with specific planning times were deemed necessary. Participants highlighted the **need for longer biomethane windows, more secure network connection times, improved infrastructure, and predictable costs associated with connecting to existing networks**. In that context, participants further discussed the importance of authorities providing a clear and accessible overview of biomass procurement costs for biomethane over the next 15 years. Without this guarantee, farmers may be hesitant to invest in the upgrade to biomethane.

Additionally, there was a call to **foster synergies with other European projects in the field**, facilitating the sharing of experiences and research. Multiple projects with similar goals were encouraged to collaborate on awareness campaigns.

Moreover, participants requested **meetings with the population to provide accurate information countering preconceptions held by anti-biogas committees**. Clear and comprehensive analyses of the environmental impact were deemed essential to avoid denigrating the sector and to raise awareness among civil society through precise documentation. Lastly, meetings with policy-makers were also requested to highlight the sector's needs, such as the missing decree on guarantees of origin.

3.4.4.4 Capacity-building programmes - Support Plan

During the discussions, several capacity-building activities were identified to support the adoption and utilization of biogas and biofuels, particularly biomethane. It was emphasized that **training courses should be provided to public administrations**, particularly in Southern Italy, to enable them to efficiently assist and guide stakeholders in navigating the procedures associated with biogas and biofuel adoption. By equipping public administrators with the necessary knowledge and tools, they can effectively support the implementation of these renewable energy sources.

One significant aspect highlighted by private manufacturers of electric biogas plants was the **need for seminars aimed at helping farmers make informed decisions between opting for biomethane or electric biogas**. In fact, the transition to biomethane for the majority of Italian farms is not a plausible prediction, and even less can it be "imposed". The economic and social fabric of livestock farms in Italy, in fact, is made up of medium-small farms, with less than 100 animals being milked, with rare exceptions in the Po Valley, where there are farms with decidedly larger numbers. A small to medium-sized farm (e.g. 70/80 head of cattle, max. 130/150) cannot access biomethane, but, where not already present, it should be encouraged and informed about the possibility of installing a small electric biogas plant.

To explore the market outlets and possibilities for biomethane in various final uses, participants recommended organizing seminars. Additionally, recognizing the diverse nature of biogas and biomethane production, it was suggested that **thematic seminars be conducted to address the specific needs and considerations associated with different types of biogas and biomethane projects**. Factors such as farm size, type of farming (e.g., livestock breeding), and scale of production should be taken into account. By tailoring the information and guidance to the specific context, stakeholders can make more informed decisions and effectively leverage the benefits offered by biogas and biomethane.

In terms of capacity-building for policymakers, **training courses and knowledge transfer by biogas plant producers** have been requested. Furthermore, participants highlighted the importance

of courses emphasizing the significance of integrating parallel production processes with primary production to maximize the value and efficiency of biogas and biomethane plants.

Research and innovation were also identified as key areas of focus, where participants called for initiatives that would explore advancements in biomass digestion techniques, the management of fermentative intermediates and waste valorisation. Lastly, with respect to biomethane upgrading, **a seminar specifically addressing the issue of distribution grids**, to support biofuels producers to evaluate whether it is convenient to connect to medium-small grids.

Table 17. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Italy

<i>Capacity-building Programmes Support Plan - IT</i>	
Type of capacity-building programmes required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training courses for public administrations on biogas adoption procedures • Seminars for farmers to understand the choice between biomethane and electric biogas • Seminars on market outlets for biomethane and different types of biogas/biomethane • Training courses for policymakers on biogas and knowledge transfer from plant producers • Courses on associating primary production with parallel processes to increase plant value • Seminars on research and innovation in biomass digestion and waste valorisation • Seminar on distribution grid issues for biomethane upgrading.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on quick and effective support for biogas adoption procedures • Provide clear and unbiased information to help farmers make informed decisions • Differentiate training and seminars based on farm size and type of breeding • Encourage research and innovation in biomass digestion and waste management.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials and resources on biogas adoption procedures • Experts and professionals to conduct seminars and training courses • Research and innovation funding for biomass digestion and waste valorisation.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administrations, especially in Southern Italy • Farmers, particularly those with small to medium-sized farms • Producers and stakeholders in the biogas and biofuels sector • Policymakers involved in energy and agricultural policy • Plant producers and experts in the biogas industry.

Impact Evaluation - Questions

Nothing extra was added.

3.4.5 Closing session

During the closing session, the participants repeatedly commented on the success of the workshop, both in gathering a diverse team of experts, capable of providing very heterogeneous experiences and points of view but all to be taken into consideration, and in addressing all the critical issues for the future of the sector. However, participants did not particularly appreciate virtual tools, preferring open debate, even though the visualization of the boards was helpful in pinpointing the discussion points. On another note, all participants requested to receive the materials for the two sessions and to be informed about future project activities, not only regarding the provision of services.

Overall, the main need that emerged from the workshop was to inform policy-makers and the authorities about the critical issues dictated by the uncertain and unsupportive regulatory framework.

3.4.6 Communication and Dissemination

The participants were individually selected and personally invited through customised invitation e-mails, which provided them with access to the event agenda, registration details and a consent form. Furthermore, APRE, the organizer, reposted a post about the event published on project's LinkedIn page, through Flaminia Rocca's page, with a comment in Italian, in order to allow participants a better understanding of the content.

Figure 9. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Italian workshop

3.4.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Figure 12. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Italy

3.5 Co-creation Workshop in Slovakia

3.5.1 Workshop's general information

On the 20th of June 2023, the co-creation workshop titled "Support for Biogas in Slovakia" took place as a physical event at the Falkensteiner Hotel Bratislava in Bratislava, Slovakia. The workshop had a duration of three hours, from 10:00 to 13:00 CET. The workshop, organized by PEDAL Consulting, s.r.o and co-organized by the Slovak Biogas Association (SBA), was conducted in the Slovak language.

With a total of 23 attendees, the workshop drew participants from various sectors and backgrounds interested in the development of the biogas sector in Slovakia. The content of the workshop revolved around the ALFA project and the outcomes of ALFA's initial research in the context of its WP1. Additionally, the Slovak Biogas Association presented an analysis of the biogas state-of-the-art in Slovakia, including an overview of framework conditions, barriers, and needs identified through the project's interviews and surveys. Successful case studies were also showcased. Additionally, the SBA speaker provided insights on the state of biomethane, promotional campaigns, and upcoming events related to biogas in Slovakia. The presentations were followed by an engaging Q&A session, fostering fruitful discussions among participants.

The second part of the workshop comprised interactive co-creation sessions. Participants actively validated and prioritized the main barriers, enablers, and needs within the biogas sector. Improvement areas were identified, and collaborative efforts were made to co-create support services aimed at enhancing the adoption of biogas systems. Feedback on the monitoring and evaluation framework was also gathered to ensure effective implementation and assessment of the support services. Lastly, Msc. David Kancko, the General Secretary of the Slovak Biogas Association, served as the keynote speaker, providing valuable insights and expertise throughout the workshop.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

In terms of preparatory actions, the Slovak Biogas Association was approached in mid-May with the offer to co-organize ALFA Co-creation workshop (CCW) in Slovakia. The communication took place through email and phone discussions. During the communication, the workshop's objectives, purpose, and goals were clearly conveyed, along with the desired outcomes. The essential details, such as the agreed date, format, and duration were established. The agenda and content, including interactive co-creation sessions and relevant speakers with their respective presentations, were also agreed upon. ALFA's Project manager from PEDAL met personally twice with Mr. Kanco, General Secretary of SBA, to ensure a smooth flow of activities - to go over the workshop's agenda; facilitation techniques that encourage collaboration, creativity, and open dialogue among participants; roles allocation (defining the facilitators or moderators who will lead the particular workshop sessions).

A minimum number of 15 participants were targeted for the workshop. The list of identified potential participants was co-created in order to invite a diverse group of participants (e.g., farmers, agriculture cooperatives, farmers associations, biogas producers, biogas customers (incl. grid operators), biogas technology providers and advisors, policy-makers, agencies and relevant authorities, civil society, NGOs and industry associations, researchers and academia, etc.) in order to gather different views/opinions and steer up the discussion on biogas and its support.

The workshop's agenda, which was carefully prepared in advance, placed a strong emphasis on achieving a balance between presentations, discussions/brainstorming, and co-creation sessions during the event.

The recruitment of participants was undertaken by the organizers, PEDAL Cons. and SBA, who reached out to their extensive contacts and networks. Personal contacts, phone calls, and emails were utilized to invite potential participants. In addition, various communication channels, including the organizers' websites and social media platforms, were leveraged to spread the word about the workshop. Invitations were sent well in advance, clearly outlining the purpose, objectives, and logistics of the event.

As many of the invitees were already familiar with the topic, the organizers decided not to share relevant materials, such as WP1 reports on framework conditions, market overview, perceptions, acceptance levels, and case studies, before the workshop. Instead, these materials were shared afterward, via a "Thank you" email, which provided the link to access the resources.

The actual registration process for participants was done via a [Online form registration form](#) prepared by PEDAL Cons. Market research was conducted to select the most appropriate and cost-effective venue ([Falkensteiner Hotel Bratislava](#)) with the proper seating arrangements, whiteboards, and other visual aids needed. The catering services were included in order to support the workshop activities. All was prepared in advance to ensure that the space and refreshment is comfortable and conducive to creative thinking.

List of the supporting material used during the workshop implementation

All necessary materials, such as stationery, flip charts, markers, pre-filled as well as empty sticky notes, A1 printed posters (such as prioritisation table, CHML Miro board quadrants etc.) were taken care of; as well as the specific tools (TV) or technologies/support (tech support, HDMI cables etc.) required to make sure everything was set up before the workshop.

After the workshop, the short evaluation and feedback form/Online form survey was prepared and distributed among participants to collect their overall workshop's perceptions, their feedback on the workshop's structure, including content, speakers etc. as well as their further input on the co-creation process.

3.5.2 *Participants and stakeholder groups represented*

3.5.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note taker etc.)
Stania Druskova (PEDAL Consulting)	Facilitator & speaker
David Kanco (SBA)	Facilitator & speaker
Janka Bielikova (PEDAL Consulting)	Note-taker, assistance during the interactive session's
Miroslav Horsky (Production ByHorsky s.r.o.)	Tech-support

3.5.2.2 Participants list

Participants list ⁵		
Organization	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
Ministry of Environment of SR	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
Slovak Biogas Association	Civil society	NGOs and industry associations
EnergOTerra, s. r. o.	Industry	Livestock farmer & biomass producer & agriculture cooperative with 2 biogas plants
First Farms	Industry	Livestock farmers (w/intention to build up biogas plant)
Bioplyn Budča, spol. s r.o.	Industry	Biogas producer
ELKOPLAST Slovakia, s.r.o.	Industry	Biogas technology providers & advisors

⁵ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

D2.2: Co-Creation outcomes shaped to our stakeholders needs, 31/08/2023

FirstFarms s.r.o.	Industry	Livestock farmers (w/intention to build up biogas plant)
CITA VIA, s.r.o.	Industry	Other farmers and biomass producers
Ministry of Environment of SR	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
agriKomp Bohemia s.r.o.	Industry	Biogas technology providers & advisors
Ministry of Environment of SR/Directorate for Environmental Impact Assessment	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
The National Agricultural and Food Centre	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra	Academia / Research	Researchers and academia (including a biogas plant operating as a laboratory)
The National Agricultural and Food Centre - Research Institute of Livestock Production	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
Slovak Gas Industry	Industry	Biogas customers (incl. grid operators)
Slovak Gas Industry	Industry	Biogas customers (incl. grid operators)
CHEBTECH s. r. o.	Industry	
Slovak Gas Industry - Distribution	Industry	Biogas customers (incl. grid operators)
Ministry of Economy of SR/Energy Section Department of Energy Policy	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies
Slovak Biogas Association	Civil society	NGOs and industry associations
The Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture (ÚKSÚP))	Government	Policy-makers and public authorities/agencies

3.5.3 Detailed remarks from Session 1

3.5.3.1 List of recommendations presented to the participants

Barriers	Needs
<p>Technical Barriers: Lack of technical knowledge, Feedstock availability, Digestate application, Propanisation, Lack of gas infrastructure, Lack of skilled workforce</p>	<p>Technical Support Needs: Biogas potential solutions assessment, Concept design and development of biogas systems, Technical support and consulting, Energy and environmental analyses assessing the energy and carbon footprint across the life cycle, Approval of the small chromatograph</p>
<p>Business/administrative Barriers: High investment costs, Lack of financial support, Investment Risk, Uncertain policy framework, Complex administrative and legal procedures</p>	<p>Business/Admin Support Needs: Financial evaluation, Access to finance, Business modelling and planning, Administrative support</p>
<p>Social barriers: Lack of awareness, Lack of information by citizens, Resistance to change, Low social acceptance, Odour and noise complaints</p>	<p>Awareness-raising and capacity-building activities: Awareness-raising campaigns, Capacity-building programmes</p>

3.5.3.2 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

The workshop started with a warm welcome, some technical instructions and engaging icebreaking opening activity in order to introduce participants to each other. Then a presentation session followed, where participants were introduced to the ALFA project.

The comprehensive presentation giving an overview of state-of-art analysis of biogas in Slovakia, including WP1's project outcomes, was presented by the General Secretary of Slovak Biogas Association (SBA), Mr. David, Kanco, MSC. The focus was to provide an analysis of the current state of biogas in Slovakia, including framework conditions, enablers, barriers, and needs identified throughout the project mapping and surveys as well as by SBA. Noteworthy success cases were also presented to highlight the potential and benefits of biogas systems. Additionally, the SBA speaker shared valuable insights into the state of biomethane in Slovakia, SBA's promotional campaigns aimed at raising awareness about biogas, and future events planned to further discuss and explore the biogas topic. The floor was given to the ALFA Project Manager, who delivered a comprehensive presentation on the ALFA support services offer for the uptake of biogas systems. This presentation provided participants with a clear understanding of the various ALFA support measures, services and assistance being available to stakeholders in the biogas sector in the close future.

The second part of the workshop consisted of two interactive co-creation sessions, which aimed to validate and prioritize the main barriers, enablers, and needs identified and validate to refine ALFA's prospective support measures. The participants actively engaged in discussions to define improvement areas and collaboratively generate ideas for the development of support services to promote the adoption of biogas systems. During the co-creation sessions, valuable feedback was

collected from the participants regarding the monitoring and evaluation framework proposed for the ALFA project. This feedback will contribute to refining and strengthening the framework to ensure accurate tracking and assessment of project outcomes.

Throughout the event, participants expressed their opinions and shared valuable insights on various aspects related to biogas systems. These remarks included discussions on the importance of policy support, financial incentives, knowledge exchange, and capacity-building initiatives. The open discussions allowed for a fruitful exchange of ideas and fostered a collaborative atmosphere among the participants. In addition to the general presentations shared by the ALFA project and SBA, no other significant deviations or enhancements were made to the common agenda.

During this session, stakeholders were presented with a comprehensive list of enablers, barriers, and needs related to the adoption of biogas in livestock farming. Their input and validation were sought - stakeholders were actively involved in the session and invited to validate the identified factors - firstly barriers, then needs, suggest any missing ones, and prioritize them according to their perceived level of criticality using the CHML methodology.

To facilitate the validation and prioritization process, pre-filled sticky notes containing the identified factors were provided to the participants. Facilitators noted down any additional factors suggested by the stakeholders. Through a collaborative discussion, the audience collectively agreed on the placement of the sticky notes on a printed Miro board, following the CHML methodology. Similar factors were grouped together for clarity and coherence.

The validated and grouped factors were transferred to a prioritization table, adhering to the CHML methodology. This table allowed participants to prioritize the factors based on their perceived importance and urgency in the implementation of biogas solutions. Firstly, individually, then mutually.

The interactive session facilitated productive discussions among the participants, fostering a collaborative atmosphere. The stakeholders actively engaged in validating, adding, and prioritizing the identified barriers and needs in the biogas sector. Through this collective effort, a comprehensive prioritized list of factors was established, reflecting the consensus and perspectives of the audience. Based on the prioritization exercise conducted during the session, the participants prioritized the barriers to the implementation of biogas solutions in Slovakia as follows:

Validated and prioritized barriers:

1. High investment costs, lack of subsidies and investment risk (financial barriers)
2. a. Lack of financial support (e.g., difficulties in obtaining loans); b. Land fragmentation
3. Unstable/uncertain policy environment & uncertain policy framework
4. Complex administrative and legal procedures; inadequate regulations (e.g., restrictions on manure and digestate management (sharing/transportation/its distribution on the fields); restrictions on plant size, substrate use; regulations concerning the connection to the electricity or gas network/grid; time/complexity/difficulties in obtaining permits for construction and connection of the facility to the grid
5. Availability of the feedstock, support for biodegradable waste
6. Digestate application
7. Propanisation
8. Socio-cultural barriers: lack of awareness - lack of info/incorrect perceptions, resistance to change, and low social acceptance, odour and noise complaints

9. The approval of the small chromatograph

10. Lack of technical training and knowledge, lack of knowledge on decision-making level:

⇒ lack gas infrastructure, and lack of skilled workforce => doesn't apply for Slovakia (SK - is one the most gas-infrastructure country in Europe)

Validated and prioritized needs:

1. Financial evaluation
2. Access to finance
3. Business modelling and planning
4. Biogas potential solutions assessment
5. Concept design and development of biogas systems;
6. Technical support and consulting
7. Energy and environmental analyses assessing the energy and carbon footprint across the life cycle:
8. Administrative support,
9. Capacity-building programmes
10. Awareness-raising campaigns

Table 18. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Slovakia categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment costs, lack of subsidies and investment risk (financial barriers) • Lack of financial support (e.g., difficulties in obtaining loans); land fragmentation • Unstable/uncertain policy environment & uncertain policy framework • Complex administrative and legal procedures, incl. authorisation process and inadequate regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of the feedstock, support for biodegradable waste • Digestate application • Propanisation • Socio-cultural barriers: lack of awareness - lack of info/incorrect perceptions, resistance to change, and low social acceptance, odour and noise complaints 	The approval of the small chromatograph	Lack of technical training and knowledge, lack of knowledge on decision-making level

Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial evaluation • Access to finance • Business modelling and planning • Biogas potential solutions assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept design and development of biogas systems • Technical support and consulting • Energy and environmental analyses assessing the energy and carbon footprint across the life cycle • Administrative support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building programmes • Awareness-raising campaigns
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Overall, the interactive session focusing on the validation and prioritization of barriers and needs in the biogas sector in Slovakia provided valuable insights from key stakeholders. The utilization of the CHML methodology ensured a systematic approach to prioritize the identified factors. The outcomes of this session will serve as essential inputs for decision-making processes within the ALFA project, contributing to the effective development and implementation of support services.

3.5.3.3 Interactive Session 1 - Additional priorities provided by participants

Participants identified further priorities, already mentioned above, to be considered, including:

- Lack of financial support (e.g., difficulties in obtaining loans) - this led to the specific support service needed combining e.g., business modelling and planning with biogas assessment in order to provide financial institutions, such as banks with the relevant and sufficient documents for obtaining a loan for the biogas plant (co)financing;
- The excessive land fragmentation;
- Inadequate regulations and the restrictions on manure and digestate management were highlighted (sharing/transportation/its distribution on the fields); restrictions on plant size, substrate use; regulations concerning the connection to the electricity or gas network/grid; time/complexity/difficulties in obtaining permits for construction and connection of the facility to the grid;
- Availability of the feedstock, support for biodegradable waste;
- Digestate application;
- Propanisation.

3.5.4.3 Interactive Session 1 – Final ranking: Top recommendations

- **Business support:**

1. Access to finance (financial barriers such as high investment costs, lack of subsidies, investment risk, lack of financial support (e.g., difficulties in obtaining loans);

- 2. Business modelling and planning;
 - 3. Administrative support connected with the complex administrative and legal procedures; inadequate regulations and the restrictions on manure and digestate management were highlighted (sharing/transportation/its distribution on the fields); restrictions on plant size, substrate use; regulations concerning the connection to the electricity or gas network/grid; time/complexity/difficulties in obtaining permits for construction and connection of the facility to the grid.
- **Technical support:**
 - 1. Biogas solutions potential assessment;
 - 2. Concept design and development of biogas systems;
 - 3. Energy and environmental analyses.
 - **Awareness-raising:** According to the participants, awareness-raising activities are not as crucial as the previously mentioned business and technical support services. If the goal is to raise awareness, practical examples, success cases, and best practices will have a much greater impact than a regular campaign. It would be more effective to showcase and share these examples.
 - **Capacity-building:** While it may be necessary, it is not of utmost importance.

The Open Panel method was employed for both part of the co-creation session, allowing for open and collaborative discussions among participants.

Overall, participants noted that it is essential to consider adjusting our services in response to the needs and preferences of the biogas industry in Slovakia. One aspect is the increasing interest among biogas plants in Slovakia in biomethane upgrade solutions. Exploring and providing support in this area would be beneficial, enabling biogas plant operators to transition from biogas to biomethane production. Additionally, many biogas plants in Slovakia are considering the option of incorporating bio-degradable kitchen waste as one of their feedstocks. Offering guidance and assistance in utilizing this type of waste would help optimize their operations and enhance the sustainability of their biogas projects.

3.5.4 Detailed remarks from Session 2

3.5.4.1 Business/Financial Services - Support Plan

During the discussion on business and financial support services, several key remarks were made. These remarks highlighted various challenges and areas where support is needed. The main remarks are presented in Table 19:

Table 19. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Slovakia

<i>Business/Financial Support Services Support Plan - SK</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance (financial barriers such as high investment costs, lack of subsidies, investment risk, lack of financial support (e.g., difficulties in obtaining loans)) • Business modelling and planning • Administrative support connected with the complex administrative and legal procedures; inadequate regulations the restrictions on manure and

	<p>digestate management were highlighted (sharing/transportation/its distribution on the fields); restrictions on plant size, substrate use; regulations concerning the connection to the electricity or gas network/grid; time/complexity/difficulties in obtaining permits for construction and connection of the facility to the grid.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal advice for farmers including legal guidance to farmers on regulatory requirements, permits, and compliance related to biogas production;
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For access to finance specifically participants provided the following recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Loans from financial institutions (e.g., banks), but since there are difficulties in obtaining a bank loan, participants recommended: → Communication with banks should be initiated in advance to understand their requirements (incl. the application process with the required docs) when applying for a loan to install or upgrade the biogas plant; → Support with the relevant documentation preparation - administrative support, as well as the importance of effective business modelling and planning was emphasized. Participants expressed the need for guidance on developing a qualitative business plan needed by banks that considers the availability and relevance of inputs and feedstock; → Raising awareness among banks about the benefits and return on investment of biogas systems was deemed crucial. → Identification of European, regional and national financing opportunities to implement biogas technologies in livestock farming - online training suggested → Step-by-step directions on how to secure financing, including information on national subsidies and online training for public officers evaluating submitted applications was suggested, given the prolonged duration for receiving feedback on submitted applications. • Participants recommended customizing services with a focus on tailored support in business modelling and planning to align with bank requirements for practical and tangible results • Delivery formats: Online training, individual consultations, and a comprehensive "HOW-TO-MANUAL" in leaflet or guidelines form. • Engage potential participants through direct outreach to organizations such as the Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber (SPPK), AKS (Chamber of Agrarian Industry of Slovakia), SBA (Slovak Biogas Association), ASYF (Association of Slovak Young Farmers), and gas industry associations, promoting the services and encouraging them to share with their members and networks.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of Eligible Stakeholders Actively Engaging with ALFA Activities and Utilizing Offered Support Services - e.g., number of participants participated in different ALFA activities/attending training sessions (webinars, seminars), seeking consultations (via hubs), or

accessing online resources (Engagement Platform, Knowledge Centre, Forum etc.); newsletters subscribers.

- **Level of Satisfaction with the Provided Services:** questions can focus on the quality, relevance, and usefulness of the services provided (e.g. *Have all your questions been answered? Was the support provided/given sufficient? What was the real result of the provided service - did you get a bank loan? Do I see improvement in my business operations (cost savings, revenue growth, increased productivity etc.)?*)
- **Assessment of Stakeholders' Knowledge and Skills Acquired through Support Services** - e.g., pre- and post-assessments measurement or self-reported evaluations.
- **Adoption rate:** to determine the extent to which the stakeholders have implemented the knowledge, skills, and recommendations acquired through the support services. This can include tracking the number of stakeholders who have implemented changes or improvements in their business practices.
- **Level of Networking Facilitated by ALFA's Support Services:** e.g., among stakeholders facilitated by the support services related mostly farmer to farmer advice, but might apply to other ALFA activities as well (mutual learning workshops, field visits, networking events, capacity building programs etc.), tracking the number of partnerships formed, joint projects initiated, or knowledge sharing activities undertaken.

The session did not identify a **direct relevance to gender balance** in the context of business and financial support services for biogas systems, as these are needed fully regardless of gender. But some financial institutions/banks offer special programs/loans for female entrepreneurs, which might be encouraging for the participation and engagement of female farmers and other underrepresented groups in the biogas value chain.

3.5.4.2 Technical Services - Support Plan

Table 20. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Slovakia

<i>Technical Support Services Support Plan - SK</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support and consultations to address specific challenges and provide guidance throughout the biogas system implementation process; • Evaluation of biogas potential based on preliminary calculations e.g. assessing the biogas potential of different substrates/mix of input raw materials/feedstock and their efficiency • Concept design and development of biogas systems; • Energy and environmental analysis assessing the energy and carbon footprint across the life cycle • Biogas solutions potential assessment investigating and evaluating possible solutions for utilizing the produced biogas. The participants prioritize analysing the financial aspects of implementing a biogas system and emphasize the importance of return on investment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust support service #6 - Evaluation and comparison of plant suppliers' quotes: Expand to recommend suitable technology based on specific needs, such as upgrading to biomethane or incorporating bio-degradable waste, ensuring efficient biogas/biomethane production. • Advice on digestate handling and application: guidance on proper handling and application of digestate, considering environmental and agronomic factors.
<p>Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preferred formats for delivering technical support services: Remote support through video conferencing, email, or dedicated platforms, enabling accessibility regardless of location. Provision of manuals and step-by-step guides for self-paced learning and convenience. • Ensure accessibility for individuals with different expertise and resources: Use clean and simplified language, offer different levels of support (basic for beginners, advanced for experienced stakeholders). • <u>Recommendations for reaching potential participants of technical support services are similar to those for business and financial services.</u>
<p>Impact Evaluation - Questions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To which extent have the services influenced real actions meaning the practical impact of the services on stakeholders' day-to-day activities; • Economic indicators to measure the financial impact of the technical support services by assessing factors such as cost savings, increased revenue, return on investment, or profitability of the supported biogas projects; • Environmental impact: the environmental benefits resulting from the implementation of the recommended practices or technologies (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions reduction, energy efficiency improvements, or waste management effectiveness).

3.5.4.3 Awareness-raising activities - Support Plan

The participants emphasized the importance of business and technical support services over awareness-raising activities. While they acknowledged the value of awareness-raising, they believed that practical examples, success cases, and best practices would have a more significant impact than a traditional campaign. Overall, their suggestions are presented in Table 21:

Table 21. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Slovakia

<i>Awareness-raising Activities Support Plan - SK</i>	
<p>Type of awareness-raising activities required</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different events such as stakeholder workshops, round tables, conferences, info days; • Targeted campaigns; • Success stories and case studies: Document and share success stories of stakeholders who have benefited from the support services. These

	<p>stories can highlight the positive impact on their business operations, financial performance, or sustainability.</p>
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizing stakeholder workshops, round tables, and conferences with dedicated discussion time is the preferred approach. • Physical meetings are preferred for ongoing communication and collaboration, promoting engagement regardless of geographical location.
Messages to focus on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailor-messaged to specific stakeholder groups (e.g., for farmers/agriculture cooperatives concentrated on cost savings; for public - in terms of environmental sustainability, waste management, and renewable energy generation); • Visually attractive messages (videos, virtual tours and/or real field visits, etc.); • Testimonials, showcasing success cases of those who have experienced the positive outcomes of implementing biogas systems. This helps to create relatable narratives that inspire and motivate others to adopt similar practices; • Examples of good practices; • FAQ on the website; • Events of different themes, such as compliance with legislative requirements, involvement in international projects, food safety, application of digestate and organic matter, examples of good practice; • HOW-TO Manual easy to find, oriented in and download.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers/agriculture cooperatives, associations and organizations • Biogas producers/plants/owners • Farmers/biogas plant owners considering biomethane production upgrades, biogas technology providers, and relevant public entities proposed or contacted during previous ALFA stakeholder consultation activities
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre- and post-campaign surveys for comparative analysis of knowledge and attitude changes. Example questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → <i>Have you gained new knowledge about biogas solutions using manure through this campaign?</i> → <i>Has your perception or acceptance of biogas solutions using manure changed as a result of this campaign?</i> → <i>Did the campaign provide useful information that influenced your understanding or decision-making regarding biogas solutions?</i>

Furthermore, to effectively spread the word, **the participants recommended utilizing communication channels of various relevant associations, organizations, and chambers.** They emphasized the importance of utilizing the most efficient channels used by these entities to reach out to their members. While social media platforms may be effective in reaching young farmers, specific topic-related workshops focused on areas such as digestate and organic matter

application, food safety, and involvement in international projects were considered more likely to attract participants from diverse stakeholder groups and effectively disseminate information.

When it comes to **raising awareness about biogas systems**, the barriers or challenges identified tend to revolve around common themes. These include a **lack of knowledge about biogas systems and their benefits**, as well as **financial constraints** stemming from high initial investment costs. However, these financial challenges can be mitigated by effectively communicating the long-term financial benefits of adopting biogas systems. Another significant challenge lies in **navigating complex administrative and legal procedures** associated with implementing such systems. By simplifying processes and providing clear guidance, this hurdle can be overcome. Additionally, negative perceptions and misconceptions surrounding biogas systems, such as concerns about odour, noise, or environmental impacts, need to be addressed. This can be achieved through the dissemination of accurate information and the promotion of positive narratives that highlight the advantages and sustainability of biogas systems.

To gather support for ALFA's awareness-raising campaigns, it is important to engage with the aforementioned networks. These networks include renewable energy associations and organizations, environmental organizations that promote clean energy and sustainable farming practices, as well as government agencies and ministries responsible for agriculture, energy, and environmental policies. By involving these diverse stakeholders, the effectiveness and reach of the awareness-raising campaigns can be significantly enhanced.

Some events to consider for raising awareness include:

- the Agricultural Fairs and Exhibitions such as [48th International Agricultural and Food Exhibition Agrokomplex](#), and or biogas conferences (e.g., [9th SBA Professional Conference - The Future of Slovak Biogas 2023](#));
- join sustainable farming networks, if available.

To attract more farmers and key actors in the biogas value chain, our awareness-raising campaigns might include specific actions, such as already-mentioned case studies, **success stories to highlight the positive impact of biogas systems and field visits to operational biogas plants showcasing their functioning and benefits**. Providing farmers and key stakeholders with hands-on experience is crucial for understanding the practical aspects and economic benefits of adopting biogas systems. Additionally, it is essential to offer clear and comprehensive information regarding available financial support options, subsidies, and incentives for implementing such systems. Emphasizing the potential return on investment and cost-saving benefits can help generate interest among farmers and key stakeholders. By highlighting these advantages, it becomes easier to showcase the value and potential gains associated with embracing biogas technology.

To encourage the participation and engagement of female farmers and other underrepresented groups in the biogas value chain, it is important to **adopt gender-inclusive language and messaging**. This means using language and communication strategies that are inclusive and respectful of diverse gender identities.

3.5.4.4 Capacity-building activities - Support Plan

According to the workshop participants, while capacity building activities might be beneficial, they were not considered essential. The results from this discussion are presented in Table 22:

Table 22. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Slovakia

<i>Capacity-building Programmes Support Plan - SK</i>	
Type of capacity-building programmes required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste management/treatment and biogas plants: many participants were additionally mentioning other types of biodegradable waste as potential feedstock for biogas plants; • Biomethane production: this topic was identified by the Slovak Biogas Association as it was noted during the workshop that there is a high level of interest among biogas plants and companies in upgrading their systems to produce biomethane; • Success stories: there is a demand for success stories showcasing the best case-studies from various regions. This topic could be further enhanced by providing an overview of the biogas plant landscape in other EU countries and comparing it to the situation in the Slovak Republic. • Additional topics proposed⁶: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Compliance with legislative requirements, <input type="checkbox"/> Application of digestate and organic matter, <input type="checkbox"/> Examples of good practice and knowledge-sharing events for the biogas value chain, <input type="checkbox"/> Q&A and step-by-step guide for installing a biogas plant.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars and capacity-building activities in the Slovak language through collaboration with relevant associations or organizations • Partnerships with associations to promote events and engage their members • Utilize advisory services and training programs offered by biogas technology providers for ALFA seminars • Collaborate with RES associations and clean energy organizations for education and awareness-raising campaigns • Maximize impact through collaboration with stakeholders to enrich the Engagement Platform and leverage their networks and resources.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks, experts, materials • ALFA tools, including the Engagement Platform and Knowledge Centre

⁶ Some of the topics suggested via the feedback form include solutions for inputs to biogas plants during agricultural crop shortages, the experience of biogas plants with the collection of biodegradable waste, advantages and disadvantages of agricultural and waste biogas plants, biogas plant sludge treatment in practice, etc.

<p>Target groups</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public officers / Authorization offices / Public agencies • Banks / Financial institutions • Farmers / Agricultural associations • Biogas producers • Policy-makers
<p>Impact Evaluation - Questions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and skills acquisition measured through the assessment or survey before and after the capacity building; • No. of participants/seminars/webinars, overall satisfaction; • Practical application of knowledge and impact evaluation through follow-up evaluation, such as conducting interviews or surveys with seminar participants. Example questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>How the seminar/webinar met your expectations content/quality/format/speakers/exchange of knowledge/effectiveness for your business (Please rate from 1-5 rating)</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Did the seminar/webinar address your learning needs and expectations regarding biogas systems?</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Did the seminar/webinar provide practical insights and tools that you can apply in your biogas projects or initiatives?</i> • <i>Do you feel more confident and prepared to implement and manage biogas systems after attending the seminar?</i>

3.5.5 Closing session

The workshop successfully achieved its objectives of introducing the ALFA project, providing an overview of the biogas landscape in Slovakia, and facilitating interactive co-creation sessions to identify improvement areas and generate ideas for support services. The active participation and insightful contributions from the attendees ensured a productive and engaging workshop. The valuable feedback received will inform the further development and implementation of the ALFA project and its support services for the biogas sector in Slovakia.

Due to the time constraints during the interactive sessions, participants were encouraged to provide their feedback and overall suggestions and express their willingness to participate in future activities organized by ALFA through the feedback form (Online form) sent as a part of the "thank you email" (with the link to all relevant materials resulting from ALFA's initial research activities from WP1) after the workshop. As reported in the beginning of the section, the participants generally displayed a positive attitude and expressed their interest in actively engaging with ALFA's initiatives.

3.5.6 *Communication and Dissemination*

Prior to the event, a set of comprehensive dissemination and communication activities were carried out to create awareness and generate interest among the target audience such as:

- A dedicated event page was created on the project website, providing detailed information about the workshop and its objectives (24.5.2023): **ALFA CCW workshop invitation: Biogas' support in Slovakia/Support for biogas in Slovakia/[Pozvánka na workshop: Podpora bioplynu na Slovensku](#)**
- Social media posts were made on social media platforms ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#)) to promote the event, including key details and registration information (24.5.2023): **ALFA CCW workshop invitation: Biogas' support in Slovakia/Support for biogas in Slovakia**
- **Social media re-posts to promote invitation for the ALFA CCW workshop**, 12.6.2023: ALFA CCW workshop invitation: Biogas' support in Slovakia/Support for biogas in Slovakia ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#))
- **Email invitations** were sent to relevant stakeholders, including industry professionals, researchers, and policymakers.

To ensure the continuity of communication and knowledge dissemination, the following activities were undertaken after the workshop:

- **Thank you email to all workshop participants:** After the workshop the email was sent to all workshop participants to appreciate their participation as well as active engagement during the workshop. The participants were encouraged to provide their feedback, overall suggestions and express their willingness to participate in future activities organized by ALFA through the feedback form (Online form). Also, the link to all relevant material (such as WP1 reports - Framework conditions, Overview of Slovak market conditions, Perceptions, acceptance levels and needs on biogas, Case studies etc.) as well as the website and social media access were provided in order to spread the word about the project and its activities;
- **Post-event Posts:** The posts were published on the PEDAL' social media summarizing the key discussions, outcomes, and recommendations from the workshop - social media posts on ALFA CCW workshop's insights/outcomes, 26.6.2023: **Postrehy z workshopu o bioplyne.** ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#))

Overall, the dissemination and communications activities before, during, and after the event played a crucial role in raising awareness, attracting participants, and ensuring effective knowledge transfer. The material distributed, along with the online presence and engagement, contributed to the success of the event and the broader dissemination of its outcomes.

3.5.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Figure 13. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Slovakia

3.6.1 Workshop's general information

The Spanish workshop titled "Desbloqueando el potencial del biogás en el sector ganadero español" or "Unlocking the biogas potential in the Spanish livestock sector" was held online on 6th July 2023 and included an open panel discussion. The event was organized by Sustainable Innovations

Europe (SIE), in collaboration with the Spanish Biogas Association (AEBIG) and Nedgia (natural gas distributor part of Naturgy – Spanish multinational natural gas and electrical supply company).

The content presented during the workshop followed a common agenda provided by WR. The main points addressed in the workshop included a comparison between the European and Spanish landscapes regarding barriers and enabling factors studied in previous project activities. The participants engaged in discussions on the seminar topic, which covered the basics of biogas (biogas 101) and expressed their opinions on the value of this information. Furthermore, there were discussions on technical and business services related to biogas, as well as awareness-raising campaigns.

Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

The preparatory actions for the co-creation workshop began by searching for suitable entities that could host the workshop and attract a wide range of stakeholders. AEBIG played a crucial role in assisting the Spanish hub with the organization and establishing a connection between ALFA and Nedgia, a prominent natural gas supplier in the country. Following several meetings held around May, the three co-hosts successfully reached an agreement on the workshop format (online), the date (06/07), and the approach to promote the event.

List of promoting actions:

1. Sent emails to stakeholders in SIE's network, around 45 stakeholders were contacted via email, once from June 16th to 18th and then a reminder on June 27th for those that had not registered.
2. One social media post through SIE's social media network inviting others to join.
3. Invitation email to all AEBIG members, including a broad list of farmers, farmer associations, technology providers and academia stakeholders, for a total of 111 people.

In general, email invitations proved to be effective, particularly when sent by a prominent association like AEBIG. The majority of registrations were received shortly after the emails were sent from their accounts, as well as following the email invitations and reminders sent to SIE's network.

3.6.2 Participants and stakeholder groups represented

3.6.2.1 Organisers

Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note taker etc.)
Carla Sebastiani	Host
Estíbaliz Garmendia	Host / Facilitator
Mariana Fernández	Tech support

3.6.2.2 Participants list

Participants list ⁷		
Organisation	QH Category	Specific stakeholder group (e.g. biomass producer, farmer, etc.)
SENER	Academia / Industry	Engineering and technology construction group
Perfect Farming	Industry	Emissions reduction service provider
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	Biogas and RES consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	RES consultancy and technology providers
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Academia/Research	Research
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	ESCO
Nippon Gases	Industry	Gas solution providers
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	RES consultancy
Capwatt	Industry	Integrated energy solutions consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	Integrated energy solutions consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	Energy investment firm
RIC Energy	Industry	RES consultancy

⁷ **Note:** The personal information (names) of the workshop's participants is accessible solely to the European Commission and will not be made public, as the deliverable is intended for public dissemination.

The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	RES consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	RES consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	ESCO
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	RES consultancy
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry	Cogeneration plant provider
RIC Energy	Industry	RES consultancy
Goener	Industry	RES consultancy
Barcelona University	Academia/Research	Researcher
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry / Civil Society	Energy supplier / Spanish Biogas Association
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Academia/Research	Energy Research Centre
The participant wished to keep his/her organization's participation anonymous.	Industry / Civil Society	Spanish Biogas Association

3.6.3 Detailed remarks from Session 1

During the session, the main guidelines provided by WR were followed, but slight adjustments were made to the presentation. The focus was placed on highlighting and discussing the specific findings for Spain, comparing them with the rest of Europe. No additional topics were introduced, and the discussions primarily took place during the co-creation sessions, which were facilitated by Carla Sebastiani (SIE).

3.6.3.1 List of recommendations presented to the participants

Barriers	Needs
<p>Technical Barriers: Lack of technical capacity; Lack of technical knowledge; Difficulty to connect to the electricity/gas network</p>	<p>Technical Support Needs: Concept design and development of biogas solutions; Evaluation of the potential of biogas solutions; Technical assistance and consulting; Advice on the implementation and maintenance of biogas solutions</p>
<p>Business/administrative Barriers: Uncertain policy and regulatory framework; Complex administrative and legal procedures; High investment costs; Uncertain ROI; Lack of financial support; Investment risks</p>	<p>Business/Admin Support Needs: Administrative support; Access to finance; Financial evaluation; Business modelling and planning</p>
<p>Social barriers: Lack of information, Poor social acceptance</p>	<p>Awareness-raising and capacity-building activities: Awareness campaigns, Capacity-building programmes for professionals of the agricultural sector; Stakeholder awareness about the value of the technology</p>

3.6.3.2 Interactive Session 1 – CHML Prioritization

The barriers that were considered by the workshop's participants to be the most crucial ones in Spain were of different nature, namely an **uncertain policy and regulatory framework**, **high investment costs**, and a **lack of information by farmers** on the benefits of biogas.

High-urgency barriers in the Spanish livestock farming landscape include the following: first, the fact that the **return on investment for biogas plants in farms remains unclear**, from the participants' perspective; second, a **lack of technical knowledge by farmers**; and third, relatedly, a **lack of technical capacity/skills** in relation to the planning, design, implementation and maintenance of biogas and biomethane technologies.

Less urgent but still relevant barriers included the **low acceptance of biogas plants** using manure by the general population and a **difficulty to connect the biogas plants in farms to the local electricity and/or gas networks**.

Lastly, investment risk, lack of financial support, complex administrative and legal procedures and difficulty to transport manure were argued to be low-urgency barriers. Interestingly, these represent barriers of the same nature as some of those considered to be the most crucial ones, namely the legal and business-related factors. Therefore, the difference appears to be on the details: while administrative and legal barriers may not be considered overly complex, the uncertainty of the current political and regulatory landscape represents a crucial limiting factor. In addition, it is not the risk of the investment nor the availability of financing sources that present an overwhelming concern, but rather the size of the investments. For reference, two of the three successful cases of biogas plants in Spanish farms, studied within the context of ALFA's task T1.3, consisted of multi-million-euro investments.

In line with the above, the most critical needs identified were **administrative support**, **access to finance**, and **concept design and development** of biogas systems. Other needs that are not

considered to be so urgent but still need to be addressed promptly include **support with the financial evaluation of investments in biogas plants** and **business modelling and planning**.

The following needs were considered to have a ‘medium’ urgency: technical assistance and consulting, the evaluation of the potential of biogas solutions, and raising awareness about the value of biogas technology to all stakeholders. While these factors are not as essential as the ones above, addressing them would still make the investment conditions in the region considerably more favourable. Lastly, general awareness-raising campaigns and advice on the implementation and maintenance of biogas solutions were ranked the lowest in terms of urgency.

Table 23. Needs and barriers for the uptake of biogas systems in livestock farming in Spain categorized by the CHML methodology

	<i>Critical-Urgency</i>	<i>High-Urgency</i>	<i>Medium-Urgency</i>	<i>Low-Urgency</i>
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertain policy and regulatory framework High investment costs Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertain return on investment Lack of technical capacity Lack of technical knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poor social acceptance Difficulty to connect to the electricity/gas network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment risks Lack of financial support Complex administrative and legal procedures Manure transportation
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept design and development of biogas solutions Access to finance Administrative support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial evaluation Business modelling and planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions Technical assistance and consulting Evaluation of the potential of biogas solutions Stakeholder awareness about the value of the technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness campaigns Advice on the implementation and maintenance of biogas solutions

3.6.3.3 Additional priorities provided by participants

An additional barrier highlighted by the workshop’s participants was related to the existing **technical limitations for the collection and transport of manure**. However, this was categorized as a low-urgency challenge when discussing it.

3.6.3.4 Interactive Session 1 – Final ranking: Top recommendations

- **Business support:**
 1. Uncertain policy and regulatory framework;
 2. High investment costs;
 3. Administrative support;
 4. Financial evaluation.
- **Technical support:**
 1. Lack of technical knowledge;
 2. Technical assistance and consultancy;
 3. Assessment on implementation and maintenance of biogas plants;
 4. Conceptual design and development of biogas systems.
- **Awareness-raising:**
 1. Awareness raising required due to lack of information on benefits of biogas (specific added value for each stakeholder is not clear).
- **Capacity-building:**
 1. Lack of training, especially in the technical part.

3.6.4 Detailed remarks from Session 2

Session 2 consisted in taking the most voted challenges and barriers and relating and discussing each of the sections of interest for the project, which were divided into (a) business and financial support, (b) technical support, (c) capacity building, and (d) awareness raising campaigns. Each of the most voted challenges (approx. 3 cards per topic) were used as a focus for the discussions and were located at the top of the respective pages where the participants were encouraged to drag the service numbers of the ones they believed were more relevant. To serve as support, SIE added to the general template the proposal of services and capacity building courses that was previously worked by SIE and the consortium in order to serve as basis for the participants.

The participants dragged the proposed service numbers to the section “type of business services required for the region,” and then they also had the opportunity to propose new services, for this they could use empty cards to write new proposals and could also interact through the zoom call to further explain their points. After the participants chose the services that they thought were relevant for the region, they were asked also to provide inputs on the implementation of said services regarding improvement of the proposal, format of the services (online, physical, etc), how to assess the impact of the services and potential KPIs we could use to see the level of impact these services had.

The same was done for the technical services, the capacity-building programmes and the key messages for the aware raising campaigns.

3.6.4.1 Business/Financial Services - Support Plan

First, the discussion in this theme started by asking participants what types of ALFA services they believed that would be the most beneficial for the region. These were, first, **business modelling and planning** (i.e. the development of innovative business models to valorise the energy and

digestate, adapted to the needs and specificities of the region), and second, **support to access finance** (i.e. the identification and step-by-step explanation of opportunities for raising funds to implement biogas technologies in livestock farming, whether at the EU, state or regional levels).

Besides these preliminary services already suggested by the workshop organisers, the participants mentioned additional types of services that would also be interesting to overcome the main barriers and needs at the business level. More specifically, they suggested **offering a certification showing the reductions in emissions arising from the operation of the biogas plant**, and an explanation of novel revenue opportunities from the carbon market (from the offsetting of CO₂ emissions).

Regarding the specific ways or channels through which these services could be provided, participants suggested the **use of virtual reality (VR) in the training sessions**.

Finally, to monitor the success of ALFA's support measures, additional relevant indicators to evaluate the impact of the business-related services would be the satisfaction of the people that receive such services and their applications for finance and/or evaluation.

Table 24. Summary of the co-created support plan for the business/financial support services in Spain

<i>Business/Financial Support Services Support Plan – ES</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business modelling • Access to finance • Certification of emission reductions • New revenue opportunities, carbon market benefits
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VR training • Online format
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction survey for service recipients • Number of finance and evaluation services requested • They agreed with the questions provided as example.

3.6.4.2 Technical Services - Support Plan

The discussions of this sub-topic followed the same flow of the business and financial services, with the participants having available the short descriptions of each service, so they could to pick the service number they thought was more relevant for Spain's context.

Out of the options, the ones that were considered more relevant were **conceptual design and development of biogas systems, LCA analysis, implementation and maintenance of biogas plants and the assessment of potential biogas solutions**. This can be related to the lack of general and technical knowledge situation that has been identified for the region, where the need for external consultancy services for planning, implementing and maintaining these solutions becomes more relevant for the successful uptake of the technology.

Regarding implementation, the attendees thought that an **online/remote approach** would be more beneficial for all stakeholders, and especially could ease replication for other regions in the future. Using virtual reality for the implementation was one of the ideas that came up during the discussion,

also applicable for the business services, and also the need to involve all stakeholders and better showcase the value these technologies can bring to each of them.

In order to implement successfully the suggested measures, the participants proposed the **involvement of government bodies**, as well as to **highlight the importance of the technologies in contrast with the new environmental directives and regulations**. Also, once again, the importance of having an idea of the Return On Investment (ROI) tool for the project was again highlighted. No new services were proposed, the attendees thought the catalogue was a good fit for the overall needs of the country.

Additionally, to evaluate the impact of the technical services, the same strategy was proposed as for the business services: satisfaction survey for service recipients, number of services requested and implemented, and finally a measure of the reduction of risk perception for the technologies.

Table 25. Summary of the co-created support plan for the technical support services in Spain

<i>Technical Support Services Support Plan – ES</i>	
Type of ALFA Services required / Additional services required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptual design and development of biogas systems • LCA • Implementation and maintenance of biogas plants consultancy • Assessment of potential biogas solutions.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VR / online • Focus on promoting the value of biogas for all stakeholders • Involve government bodies • Use information on new environmental directives as a way to attract more stakeholders • Attendees’ interests: Biogas systems implementation, ROI analysis, and economic and environmental implications.
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction survey for service recipients • Number of technical services requested and received • Reduction in the perception of risks in biogas investment

3.6.4.3 Awareness-raising activities - Support Plan

During the awareness-raising discussions, the participants first identified the key issues and needs from all the previous sessions and then aligned the feedback with potential messages to promote the market uptake of the solutions. Again, the discussion revolved around two key points: 1) the **need to tailor the messages for each stakeholder group**, specifically from the perspective of providing useful data for interested parties (notably farmers) to be able to understand the value of

the investment, and 2) to **focus on increasing the overall knowledge on the benefits that biogas can bring to the stakeholders' day-to-day businesses.**

The ideas for the implementation of the campaigns included to involve a **ROI tool** which could boost the interest in the technologies, since the investment risk was mentioned several times during the workshop.

The primary target group should be livestock farmers, but the messages must be tailored for other stakeholders in the value-chain, such as energy suppliers, big producers, regional governments, general public, and others.

Regarding ways of measuring the impact, the attendees agreed with the sample questions presented during the session as an effective way to assess the success of the awareness-raising campaigns.

Table 26. Summary of the co-created support plan for the awareness-raising activities support services in Spain

<i>Awareness-raising Activities Support Plan - ES</i>	
Type of awareness-raising activities required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the overall knowledge of all stakeholders on the benefits of biogas and biomethane • Clarify the value that these technologies could bring to all stakeholders (multi-stakeholder approach, not only for farmers)
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of a tool to calculate return on investment could work in attracting stakeholders, since this seems to be an important factor when deciding to approach this type of projects • Engaging big producers could be the key to better support and reach farmers.
Messages to focus on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stakeholder approach, clarifying the return on investment as much as possible, or offering tools for projects to calculate ROI
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • All other stakeholders
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of key messages • Average engagement per message/campaign • Total reach • Number of challenges tackled via the campaigns

3.6.4.4 Capacity-building programmes - Support Plan

Table 27. Summary of the co-created support plan for the capacity-building activities support services in Spain

<i>Capacity-building Programmes Support Plan - ES</i>	
Type of capacity-building programmes required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall, participants were satisfied with the proposed capacity-building topics • A potential addition could be a topic focusing the economic and environmental value of the biogas systems • Proposed topic: Biogas 101 - Definitions, Manure Valorisation, and Farmer Relevance.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online materials
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • All stakeholders
Impact Evaluation - Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants • Number of seminars/webinars • Number of topics in scope • General satisfaction survey

Regarding capacity-building, the attendees considered the proposed topics (which were already tailored to Spain's needs) as a good approach considering the untapped potential of the biogas market in comparison to other ALFA regions. Additionally, in terms of capacity-building content the attendees suggested to **showcase the economic and environmental benefits of biogas systems**, while also engaging big producers to explore their potential role in adopting these technologies.

Moreover, to ensure broad accessibility, it was agreed that the implementation of the capacity-building program should be conducted in an **online format**, with all support materials provided in digital form.

The attendees also agreed with the proposed assessment criteria to measure the impact of the capacity-building programmes. These criteria include tracking the number of participants, the number of seminars/webinars held, the range of topics covered, and utilizing a general satisfaction survey to gather feedback and opinions from the participants.

3.6.5 Closing session

SIE conducted the closing session, summarizing the key points addressed throughout the workshop. During this session, the chat remained open for any questions, although no remarks were made at that time. However, after the session concluded, some attendees who had to leave early shared their remarks. SIE provided the completed Miró board to gather any additional comments from these attendees. Moreover, some participants expressed their interest in staying updated with the project activities and willingly consented to subscribe to the newsletter for further information.

In terms of relevance, the challenges discussed during the workshop can be ranked as follows:

- **Financial challenges:** The need for financial evaluation and financing support emerged as the most significant challenge. Participants emphasized the importance of addressing financial aspects in biogas projects.
- **Technical challenges:** The lack of technical knowledge regarding biogas solutions and their added values, particularly related to implementation, maintenance, and overall evaluation of available technologies and options, was identified as a key challenge.
- **Regulatory challenges:** Surprisingly, regulatory challenges were not extensively discussed during the workshop, despite their significant impact on emerging projects. However, it was acknowledged that addressing regulatory hurdles is crucial for the success of biogas initiatives.

3.6.6 Communication and Dissemination

To disseminate the webinar an event on LinkedIn was created to promote the session, an invitation was designed to send to the stakeholders, and the agenda was also drafted with the times and topics to be discussed.

The materials and activities were as follows:

- LinkedIn event: The post has 136 organic impressions.
- Link to the post: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7076818788742049792>
- Email invitation: From SIE's side around 45 stakeholders were contacted via email. The Spanish Biogas Association (AEBIG) sent the email invitation around 111 stakeholders. In total 156 were contacted.
- Agenda: The agenda was distributed to the same number of people to whom the invitation was sent. In total about 156.

Figure 15. Example of social media dissemination (LinkedIn post) for the Spanish workshop

Desbloqueando el potencial del biogás en la ganadería

AGENDA
Jueves 6 de Julio, 2023
10:00 - 12:15 (CET)

HORA	TEMA
10:00 - 10:15	Bienvenida y objetivos del taller Introducción de los socios y participantes
10:15 - 10:25	Breve presentación del proyecto y principales conclusiones
10:25 - 10:30	Presentación de los servicios de apoyo empresarial y técnico de ALFA
10:30 - 11:10	Validación y priorización de los principales obstáculos y oportunidades
11:10 - 12:00	Soluciones; debate sobre el marco de seguimiento y evaluación
12:00 - 12:15	Discusiones y conclusiones
12:15	Fin del taller

Con la participación de:

Figure 16. The agenda of the Spanish workshop

3.6.7 Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Priorización de los obstáculos

C Urgencia-Crítica
Barreras más importantes para España

- Apoyo político/regulatorio incierto
- Alzados costes de inversión
- Falta de información

A Urgencia-Alta
Obstáculos que no son tan urgentes pero que deben abordarse.

- Falta de conocimientos técnicos
- Falta de capacitación
- No está claro el retorno financiero de la inversión

M Urgencia-Media
No es un problema si no se aborda, pero sigue siendo importante.

- Falta de conocimientos técnicos
- Baja aceptación social
- Dificultad para conectarse a la red de gas/rüz

B Urgencia-Baja
Barreras que no son tan urgentes pero que deben abordarse.

- Riesgo de inversión

C Urgencia-Crítica
Necesidades que son absolutamente necesarias y deben satisfacerse.

- Apoyo administrativo
- Acceso a financiación
- Diseño conceptual y desarrollo de sistemas de biogás

A Urgencia-Alta
Necesidades que no son tan urgentes pero que deben atenderse con prontitud.

- Evaluación financiera
- Modelización y planificación empresarial
- Diseño conceptual y desarrollo de sistemas de biogás

M Urgencia-Media
Necesidades que no son esenciales, pero que podrían mejorar las condiciones regionales si se abordan.

- Asistencia técnica y asesoramiento
- Evaluación del potencial de soluciones de biogás
- Transferencia de esta tecnología para todas las partes interesadas

B Urgencia-Baja
Necesidades que tienen un impacto mínimo si no se abordan.

- Asesoramiento sobre el mantenimiento y el funcionamiento de instalaciones de biogás
- Campañas de concienciación

Figure 17. Examples of the dissemination material produced during the co-creation workshop in Spain

4. Discussion of co-created support plans

The following tables present an overview of the support services required in each of the ALFA target countries based on the feedback collected during the co-creation workshops. It is important to note that these are recommendations, and ALFA will thoroughly study and evaluate them to determine how to tailor its services or establish collaborations with external resource providers. Our intention is not to commit to delivering all the listed services, but rather to explore the most viable and impactful options.

Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Belgium	Business support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Administrative support (Flanders) Financial evaluation Access to finance (Wallonia) Business modelling and planning 	Awareness-raising: Raising technical awareness about biogas plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Develop customized business plans for biogas plant projects # Promote centralized models over decentralized ones # Advocate for energy-focused financial support # Engage in lobbying efforts for green certificates and incentives # Measure the impact by the number of generated business opportunities. Technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Offer consulting support to farmers for biogas plant operation and maintenance # Create regionally specific factsheets to provide accessible information about biogas technologies # Conduct research and communication on pollution issues like surplus ammonia emissions # Perform analysis of fermenter biology and gas quality to enhance biogas production efficiency. Awareness-raising:
	Technical support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical support and consulting 	Capacity-building: <i>Type of programmes:</i>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online seminars • Hands-on skills-building courses <p>Topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biogas plant operation and maintenance for farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Provide online resources and forms providing accessible information about biogas plants and their benefits # Emphasize accurate and reliable information to address low social acceptance and opposition # Garner support from agricultural federations and policy-makers by demonstrating the benefits of biogas plants # Leverage existing networks of research centres and agricultural partners for knowledge dissemination • Capacity-building: # Organization of on-site visits to operational biogas plants. # Emphasize on the economic benefits of biogas plant operation and maintenance for farmers # Collaborate with regional schools to leverage their expertise and facilities.
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Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Denmark	<p>Business & Technical support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every service provided by the project is equally significant to the participants, and therefore no further recommendations were provided regarding the introduction of new services. 	<p>Awareness-raising:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information campaigns <p>Capacity-building:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group-sharing experiences • Training for various facility employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business and technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Create a forum dedicated to optimizing processes. # Create an online resource catalogue that addresses challenges and provides solutions. # Compile an overview of viable biomasses to aid decision-making in projects. # Development of a database of successful and unsuccessful cases. # Ensure a geographical spread of the facilities with information on location. # Development of a platform to gather GIS data for agricultural purposes. • Awareness-raising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Information campaigns for authorities and neighbours. # Development of a platform to share knowledge about biogas, best practices and lessons-learned from real-world experiences. • Capacity-building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Create groups for exchange of experiences. # Update of the Danish handbook for the establishment of biogas plants and the spread of the corresponding concept to the other countries. # Provide information on novel biomass types suitable for biogas production. # Establish educational programs spanning multiple proficiency levels. # Offer opportunities for additional training for facility employees. # Establish a knowledge bank focused on biomass-related information.

Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Greece	<p>Business support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Farmer-to-farmer advice 	<p>Awareness-raising:</p> <p><i>Topics:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper use of digestate • Bioeconomy development and utilization of livestock residues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Develop a biogas plant-to-biogas plant service, similar to the farmer-to-farmer service # Actively invite and promote female participation in the biogas sector # Foster partnerships and collaborations with local livestock associations to support biogas initiatives • Technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Offer remote meetings for efficient communication between technical partners and beneficiaries # Incorporate business-related support into existing farmer-to-farmer service platforms • Awareness-raising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Leverage existing awareness campaigns to expand outreach efforts # Develop targeted educational materials and resources on digestate utilization and the bioeconomy # Utilize various communication channels, including social media, websites, and workshops, to disseminate information effectively
	<p>Technical support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas plants • Remote meetings for efficient communication between 	<p>Capacity-building:</p> <p><i>Topics:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biogas and the circular economy • Women engagement in biogas production in the livestock industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity-building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Conduct capacity-building seminars in the local language to enhance accessibility and engagement # Collaborate with livestock farmers associations to ensure effective outreach and participation # Involve agronomists in capacity-building activities to promote the benefits of digestate as fertilizer # Incorporate gender considerations and mainstreaming into plant activities and management practices.

D2.2: Co-Creation outcomes shaped to our stakeholders needs, 31/08/2023

	technical partners and beneficiaries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Training on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for environmental impact analysis.	
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Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Italy	Business support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial assessment Access to finance Administrative support Business modelling and planning 	Awareness-raising: <i>Topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The benefits of biogas production The benefits of electricity production with biogas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Integrate the business modelling and planning service in the context of biomethane and consider linking plant size to company characteristics # Provide an overview of various financing methods for access to finance support # Introduce a decision support service/tool Technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Knowing the Biochemical Methane Potential of biomass is crucial for the concept design and development service # Concept design services should involve feasibility studies to assist farmers in making informed choices # Need for professional technical training services focused on biomass, optimizing fermentation processes, and valorising fermentative intermediates and waste
	Technical support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical support and consulting Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions Concept design and 	Capacity-building: <i>Type of programmes:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training materials and resources on biogas adoption procedures Research and innovation funding for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness-raising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Foster collaboration with other European projects and share experiences and research # Conduct information campaigns targeting Southern Italy to educate citizens about biogas advantages # Increase awareness among authorities and provide correct information about the impact of small electric biogas plants to address social protests Capacity-building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Provide clear and unbiased information to help farmers make informed decisions # Differentiate training and seminars based on farm size and type of breeding

D2.2: Co-Creation outcomes shaped to our stakeholders needs, 31/08/2023

	development of biogas solutions	biomass digestion and waste valorisation	# Encourage research and innovation in biomass digestion and waste management.
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Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Slovakia	Business support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Business modelling and planning • Administrative support • Legal advice for farmers 	Awareness-raising: <i>Topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success stories and case studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Support with the relevant documentation preparation - administrative support # Raise awareness among banks about the benefits and return on investment of biogas systems # Identify European, regional and national financing opportunities and provide step-by-step directions on how to secure them # Customize services with a focus on tailored support in business modelling and planning to align with bank requirements for practical and tangible results • Technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Ensure accessibility for individuals with different expertise and resources
	Technical support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept design and development • Assessment of the potential of biogas solutions • Advice on digestate handling and application 	Capacity-building: <i>Topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success stories and case studies • Waste management/treatment and biogas plants • Biomethane production • Compliance with legislative requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Preferred formats for delivering technical support services: Remotely through video conferencing, or dedicated platforms, enabling accessibility regardless of location • Awareness-raising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Document and share success stories and case studies of stakeholders who have benefited from the support services # Organize stakeholder workshops, round tables, and conferences with dedicated discussion time # Physical meetings are preferred for ongoing communication and collaboration • Capacity-building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Conduct seminars and capacity-building activities in the local language, specifically Slovak, in collaboration with relevant associations or organizations to deliver services, promote events and engage their members

D2.2: Co-Creation outcomes shaped to our stakeholders needs, 31/08/2023

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Energy and environmental analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Application of digestate and organic matter• Examples of good practice and knowledge-sharing events for the biogas value chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"># Utilize advisory services and training programs offered by biogas technology providers for ALFA seminars# Collaborate with Renewable Energy Sources (RES) associations and clean energy organizations for education and awareness-raising campaigns
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Country	Support services required		Implementation
	Business & Technical	Awareness-raising and Capacity-building activities	
Spain	Business support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to finance • Business modelling and planning 	Awareness-raising: <i>Topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The benefits of biogas and biomethane 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Provide virtual reality training # Online delivery of the services preferred • Technical support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Provide virtual reality training # Online delivery of the services preferred # Involve governmental bodies # Collect and use information on new environmental directives # Promote the value of biogas for each stakeholder group
	Technical support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept design and development • Life-cycle analysis • Consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions • Assessment of the potential biogas solutions. 	Capacity-building: <i>Topics:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The economic and environmental value of the biogas systems • Biogas - Definitions, Manure Valorisation, and Farmer Relevance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness-raising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Use of a tool to calculate return on investment # Engage big producers # Clarify the value that biogas technologies could bring to all stakeholder groups • Capacity-building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Online delivery of the capacity-building programmes is preferred # Target groups include particularly farmers, but other stakeholder groups as well # Measuring the impact of the capacity-building activities could be achieved by the number of participants, seminars/webinars or topics and a general satisfaction survey.

This section offers a comparative analysis of the required support services in ALFA's target countries. First and foremost, business support appears to play a crucial role in encouraging the adoption of biogas systems in the target countries. The majority of the ALFA regions would benefit from administrative support and financial evaluation to streamline the permit approval process and assess project's feasibility, respectively. Access to finance represents another vital aspect where countries like Greece and Slovakia require assistance, as it can pose a significant obstacle to the implementation of biogas projects. Moreover, tailored business modelling and planning services are crucial to help investors to understand the economic viability and develop strategies for success.

Next, technical support assumes a critical role in ensuring the smooth operation and maintenance of biogas systems. Countries such as Greece and Slovakia stand to gain significantly from expert consultancy on the implementation and monitoring of biogas solutions. Moreover, facilitating assistance with digestate handling and application becomes imperative for promoting optimal waste management and agricultural advantages, particularly in Slovakia. In addition, technical expertise and research funding, based on Italy's requirements, become essential in optimizing fermentation processes and waste valorisation.

Moving on, the third crucial aspect involves raising awareness about the advantages of biogas systems to cultivate public acceptance and support. All of the target countries reported that would benefit from awareness-raising initiatives like success stories, case studies, on-site visits to biogas plants and targeted educational materials.

In terms of capacity-building initiatives, countries like Italy, Greece and Slovakia can benefit from organizing seminars and workshops in local languages to engage farmers and other stakeholders effectively. Furthermore, collaborations with relevant associations and livestock farmers' groups, can broaden the reach of capacity-building activities. Particularly in Denmark the participants' highlighted the need for increased educational offers and addressing the shortage of qualified labour. Additionally, providing training on life-cycle analysis was identified as an essential tool in both Greece and Spain. Notably, in Slovakia, both awareness-raising and capacity-building activities were deemed to be of less importance compared to the business and technical support services. However, overall, participants provided valuable recommendations on the various topics that the capacity-building programmes should focus on.

One prevalent suggestion was to emphasize collaboration with external partners. This approach involves leveraging the existing networks of biogas associations to expand outreach to a broader range of stakeholders. Additionally, it was recommended to form partnerships with subject matter experts who can contribute with specialized knowledge beyond the expertise of ALFA's consortium. Furthermore, participants emphasized the importance of fostering synergies with other European projects to exchange findings and experiences, thereby enhancing the overall impact of ALFA's initiatives. Collaborating with educational institutions was also highlighted, especially in developing educational materials and for capacity-building initiatives.

Another recurrent theme was the need to promote knowledge and experience sharing among different stakeholders. This included facilitating on-site visits and sharing best practices to raise awareness and provide valuable insights for farmers. Creating opportunities for hands-on learning, such as showcasing how to operate biogas plants, was seen as an effective way to build capacity among interested parties. Moreover, the concept of farmer-to-farmer or biogas plant-to-biogas plant advice service garnered attention as a means to encourage knowledge exchange and cooperation within the agricultural community.

5. Conclusions

Task 2.2 “Co-creation of solutions for biogas market uptake shaped to regional specificities and needs” of the ALFA project successfully achieved its primary goal of organizing and facilitating a co-creation workshop in each ALFA hub. These workshops were designed to collaboratively shape and develop the project’s support services to promote the adoption of biogas systems in livestock farming. In total, six workshops were conducted, one in each hub, over a 3-month period. The average participation in these workshops was substantial (18 participants external to the consortium, on average), with enthusiastic contributions from various stakeholders. Participants actively engaged in discussions, providing valuable insights and recommendations for areas of improvement in their respective countries.

Overall, the workshops proved instrumental in generating significant outcomes on both organizational and substantive levels. Participants' feedback and valuable inputs covered a broad spectrum, including recommendations on the delivery of the services, monitoring and evaluation strategies, and the consideration of interrelated aspects affecting biogas adoption, such as the handling of digestate in compliance with regulations or the need for proper information dissemination for its efficient use.

In conclusion, a successful transition towards widespread biogas system adoption in these countries requires a combination of business support, technical expertise, awareness-raising efforts, and capacity-building initiatives. Tailoring these support services to each country's specific needs and challenges will be crucial for accelerating the uptake of biogas systems and promoting sustainable energy practices on a broader scale. It is worth noting that all of the countries provided variable feedback for the delivery of the project's services, still with common elements. Among others, administrative support and financial evaluation, technical support and consultancy regarding implementation, operation and maintenance of biogas systems, or collaborating with farmers, researchers and relevant associations to showcase success stories and to develop materials for capacity-building. By incorporating this valuable feedback, the project can ensure that its support services are relevant, impactful, and better aligned with the diverse contexts and stakeholders in each country, ultimately driving the successful uptake of biogas systems and contributing to a greener and more sustainable future.

Looking ahead, ALFA's next steps involve the implementation of several related activities. The project will issue an open call to identify cases to support, transparently selecting around 8 to 9 cases per target country (at least 50 in total) based on specific criteria. The delivery of business services, such as market research, business modelling, funding access support, and sustainable finance assistance, will empower farmers and stakeholders in the livestock farming industry to embrace biogas solutions within their regions. Additionally, the project aims to provide technical assistance to the selected cases, catering to their unique needs and circumstances in deploying or improving biogas solutions.

Capacity-building activities are also planned to foster the practical uptake of biogas solutions, ensuring farmers have the necessary skills and knowledge to implement and maintain these systems effectively. Moreover, raising awareness campaigns will be conducted to build acceptance and dispel misconceptions about biogas solutions in the livestock farming sector. These campaigns seek to inform farmers about the benefits of biogas and available opportunities, as well as tackle challenges and misconceptions surrounding biogas adoption among the European population.

6. Annexes

6.1 Annex I – Workshop’s agenda

Event structure	Time	Description
Introduction	10-15'	Welcome & objectives of the workshop
		Roundtable to introduce partners and participants
Presentation of the project and WP1 findings	10-15'	Short presentation of the project and main findings combining results from <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework conditions in your region • Stakeholders’ perceptions: barriers, enablers, and needs • Preliminary results of T1.3 case studies: evidence
Presentation of the ALFA offerings	10'	Presentation of ALFA’s business and technical support services.
Co-creating market uptake measures	30-35'	Session 1: Validation and prioritization of key barriers, enablers and opportunities to be pursued; definition of improvement areas.
	5'	Break (optional)
	45-50'	Session 2: Co-creation of solutions; discussion of the monitoring and evaluation framework.
(Coffee/lunch) Break	15-30'	
Rapporteurs & Discussion	15'- 20'	5-10' for reporting; 5-10' discussion
Conclusions	5'	Wrap-up

Figure 18. The agenda template of the workshops

6.2 Annex II - Reporting template

T2.2 Co-creation workshops – Reporting Template, 07/06/2023

The following is the reporting template that should be shared with WR no later than the 14th of July.

1. Workshop General Information

Table 1. General information about the co-creation workshop

Workshop's details	Description
Title	XXX
Date	XXX
Format	XXX
Venue (if offline)	XXX
Methodology	XXX
Organiser	XXX
Audience (number of participants)	XXX
Content (besides what was presented as part of the common agenda and slides provided by WR)	<i>Briefly describe the content presented to the participants (max 300 characters): <u>if the presentation was translated in your regional language it should be included as an annex to the email, but we ask you here to summarize the main points addressed.</u></i>
Keynote speaker	<i>If a keynote speaker was present, briefly describe what was presented. If not, leave this cell empty.</i>

Table 2. Support staff and roles during the co-creation workshop

No	Moderator's name and organisation	Moderator's role (e.g. facilitator, tech support, note taker etc.)
1	XXX	XXX
2	XXX	XXX
3	XXX	XXX

1.2 Preparatory actions, supporting material, implementation remarks

Please briefly describe the preparatory actions that you followed for organising and promoting the workshop (e.g., co-organising with other entities).

Please provide a list of the supporting material used during the workshop implementation.

Please also provide a list of the promoting actions.

Preparatory actions:

List of supporting material:

- 1)
- 2)
- 3)

List of promoting actions:

- 1)
- 2)
- 3)

Feedback:

-
-

2. Detailed Remarks from the Workshop's Sessions

2.1 Introductory Session

Please provide a description of the process followed and the main remarks from your event's introductory activities (e.g. Project overview presentation, Open discussion, notes kept from opinions expressed). If extra topics were presented, compared to the general presentation shared by WR, please provide the name of the presenter, as well as the goal and theme of the presentation. If there were any other deviations or enhancements to the common agenda, please mention it briefly here or in the relevant section.

Main remarks from your event's introductory activities
(1-2 paragraphs)

2.2 Interactive session 1

2.2.1 Barriers and Needs Validation

Report here the results of the Mentimeter validation Poll. Attach the relevant printscreens.

Add the printscreen of Mentimeter results on the reported barriers.

Add the printscreen of Mentimeter results on the reported needs.

2.2.2 CHML Barriers Prioritization

Report here the results of the Mentimeter ranking Poll and the Miro board ranking table. Attach the relevant printscreens.

Add the printscreen of Mentimeter ranking results on the reported barriers.

Add the printscreen of Miroboard ranking table on the reported barriers.

2.2.3 CHML Needs Prioritization

Report here the results of the Mentimeter ranking Poll and the Miro board ranking table. Attach the relevant printscreens.

Add the printscreen of Mentimeter ranking results on the reported needs.

2.2.4 **Additional priorities provided by participants (if applicable)**

- ...
- ...

2.2.5 **Final ranking – Top recommendations**

Indicate here the top priorities selected by the participants that were used in the interactive session 2. Multiple needs/barriers may be selected for each theme, according to the results of the CHML prioritization exercise.

- Business support:
- Technical support:
- Awareness-raising:
- Capacity-building:

2.3 **2nd Session: Techniques, Questions and Answers**

Here, a report on the results of the main co-creation session follows: including the questions posed and a description of the given answers per theme. Please provide details with regard to the method implemented during your workshop (e.g., World Cafe vs Open panel). Please also note if the participants were split in different groups that worked in parallel. If your brainstorming approach was not included in the Workshops' Guidelines, please describe the following process in detail.

T2.2 Co-creation workshops – Reporting Template, 07/06/2023

<i>e.g. Method used: World-Café format</i>
<i>Main Remarks that have been discussed – Business/financial support services:</i>
.....
.....
.....
<i>Main Remarks that have been discussed – Technical support services:</i>
.....
.....
.....
<i>Main Remarks that have been discussed – Awareness raising activities:</i>
.....
.....
.....
<i>Main Remarks that have been discussed – Capacity building activities:</i>
.....
.....
.....

2.4 Closing Session

Please provide a brief description and main remarks of the workshop's closing session.

Your paragraphs should give answers to the following questions:

- Did participants provide any final remarks on the conclusions of the 2 main sessions?
- Did participants provide any overall suggestions about the workshop?
- Were participants informed of future activities? If so, did they seem to be willing to participate in ALFA's future activities (e.g., supporting with finding candidates for the delivery of services)?

*Main remarks from your event's closing activities
(1-2 paragraphs)*

3. Communication and dissemination

Briefly describe the dissemination and communications activities carried out before, during and after the event and the material distributed (brochures, posters displayed). Please also add screen captures of the posts or other communications.

Note: It is important to report the exact number of promotional material distributed (e.g. 15 leaflets).

4. Material and multimedia produced during the activities

Please, attach any digital or printed supporting material that was used before or during the workshop. Please also include pictures of your event (e.g. whiteboard with ideas, participants brainstorming, photos of the posters/screenshot of the material produced online, etc.). They should include the participants (Note: only those who gave us their consent; otherwise, the material needs to be 'anonymised').

The project

ALFA has the objective to help unlock the EU's biogas production potential by fostering the adoption of technologies using manure to produce biogas, thus helping increase the adoption of renewable energy sources in the EU and helping reduce emissions from untreated animal waste. The project will identify drivers and barriers for the uptake of biogas in the EU livestock farming industry and will support farmers from 6 EU countries (Italy, Denmark, Belgium, Slovakia, Greece and Spain) through its own co-created solutions, including financial, business, and technical support services as well as capacity-building seminars. In parallel, the project will develop an Engagement Platform to host tools that facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange among industry actors and provide credible estimations of each farm's biogas potential, prospect profits, and environmental and social impacts. Moreover, ALFA will inform all relevant stakeholders via awareness-raising campaigns and policy recommendations, and will provide guidelines for replication of its results in other regions.

Coordinator: **Q-PLAN**

PARTNER	SHORT NAME	
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	QPL
	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA	APRE
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	A0CO2
	CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS	CERTH
	FBCD AS	FBCD
	SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS EUROPE SL	SIE
	WR RESEARCH SRL	WR
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PED
	EUROPEAN DAIRY FARMERS E.V.	EDF
	EUROPEAN BIOGAS ASSOCIATION AISBL	EBA

CONTACT US: info@alfa-res.eu

VISIT: www.alfa-res.eu